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Innovative wind energy production beyond classic wind turbines – a study on experiences of new emerging wind energy exploitation technologies

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I declare in lieu of an oath that I have written this master thesis by myself, and that I did not use other sources or resources than stated for its preparation. I declare that I have clearly indicated all direct and indirect quotations, and that this thesis has not been submitted elsewhere for examination purposes.

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Abstract

The constant grow of national energy consumption rates, climate change and heavy dependence of Ireland on the exported fossil fuels and the tendency to quick depletion of these resources worldwide made an employment of renewable energy a significant concern for the country because of need to satisfy future energy demand while also ensuring the economic feasibility of renewable energy exploitation systems. This paper aims at estimating the economic viability of mast-mounted micro-scale standalone wind turbines and to assess the cost effectiveness of the sampled micro-renewable wind systems under the range of particular circumstances at the specific target location. The average wind speed data and the average annual electrical load for the Irish household within the target location will be derived by applying simulation and optimization software in order to obtain essential data for making further analysis on economic viability of the selected wind systems. The Discounted Cash Flow and Payback Period methods will be applied to obtain the results on cost effectiveness of the sampled micro-wind power generation turbines to deliver empirically and statistically grounded results. The ultimate answer to the research question will be received through comparing the data sets on the technical and economic performance of the selected wind energy technologies examined under the range of relevant conditions and scenarios.

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List of Abbreviations

AEP	Annual Energy Production
CDF	Cumulative Density Function
DCF	Discounted Cash Flow
EECA	Energy Efficiency and Conservation Authority
ESB	Electricity Supply Board
EU	European Union
EWEA	European Wind energy Association
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HAWT	Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines
HOMER	Hybrid Optimization Model for Electric Renewables
IWEA	Irish Wind Energy Association
NPV	Net Present Value
PDF	Probability Density Function
PVS	Photovoltaics System
REFIT	Renewable Electricity Feed-in Tariff
REN 21	Renewable Energy Policy Network for the 21 st Century
RPM	Rotations per Minute
SEAI	Sustainable Energy Authority Ireland
SEI	Sustainable Energy Ireland
SWT	Small Wind Turbine
TNPC	Total Net Present Cost
VAC	Voltage Alternative Current
VAT	Value Added Tax
VAWT	Vertical Axis Wind Turbines
WWEA	World Wind Energy Association

1. Introduction

1.1 Historical Background and Current Status of Wind Turbines

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is one of the basic factors which define the development of the country (Bakshi & Dhasmana, 2015). In its turn the level of growth is directly connected to amount of energy produced within the specific state. In order to assure the stable economic growth the nation should have sufficient amount of resources to generate power. Due to the drastic shortage of conventional fossil resources and the raising coefficient of CO₂ emissions worldwide, the demand for sustainable and clean source of energy has been growing day by day (Kaldellis & Zafirakis, 2011). The solution was found in discovering the potential of wind energy which is, being renewable, is capable of covering the power need of world economies due to its abundance.

A wind turbine is a specific type of technology, which is able to convert the kinetic energy of the wind stream to mechanical power and eventually into electricity (Tummala, Velamati, Sinha, Indraj, & Krishna, 2015). First prototypes of contemporary wind turbines originated around 200 B.C. in Persia. Wind mills (Fig. 1.1) were further developed by American farmers and over 6 million of small machines were used for water pumping and electricity generation between 1850 and 1970 (Dodge, 2006). The first large scale wind system which was able to generate electricity output of 12 kW was first installed in Cleveland, Ohio, in 1888 (Kaldellis & Zafirakis, 2011). The first utility grid-connected wind turbine was crafted by John Brown & Co in 1951 and due to USA government involvement in the wind energy research after the oil crisis of 1973 by the end of 1980 the wind turbines market turned from domestic scope micro turbines to the industrial scale systems with the energy output up to 600 kW (Thomas & Robbins, 1980).

The wind power capacity has increased quickly since the global energy demand constantly needs to be covered. By the end of 2014 the total worldwide capacity of wind power was approximately 369.6 GW and this number is expected to reach the target of 1000 GW by the end of 2030 (Global Energy Council, 2015).

Fig. 1.1 Wind turbines through history from a Mediterranean mill to advanced designs.

Fig. 1.1. Adapted from “The illustrated history of wind power development” by D. M. Dodge, 2006, *U.S. Federal Wind Energy Program*.

Since the energy problem is among those the humanity is most concerned of, various countries are installing large scale wind farms on shore and off shore with the primary goal to meet internal power demand and with the strategic goal to become the exporter of the energy in the future. Such a tendency has ultimately resulted in large continental wind farms. Although wind power exploitation systems are mostly perceived as environmentally friendly and have widespread social support (European Commission, 2006), one can no longer deny that these systems have significant environmental influence such as the visual and noise pollution, land use, the electromagnetic interference, the influence on population of birds and fish, and general wild life concerns (Kaldellis & Zafirakis, 2011).

The effect of wind farms on the climatic conditions has been studied by various scientists. Wang and Prinn (2010) by conducting the simulations using a three dimensional climatic model, have identified that the installation of wind farms in order to cover 10-15 percent of global power demand might cause the warming of the Earth surface by 1 °C. Fig. 1.2 demonstrates the temperature changes due to the deployment of large scale wind farms in regions.

Fig. 1.2 Temperature changes due to the deployment of large scale wind farms.

Fig. 1.2. Adapted from “Potential climatic impacts and reliability of very large-scale wind farms” by C. Wang & R. Prinn, 2010, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, p. 2056.

Another research conducted through fulfilling simulations for 62 warm seasons on a regional climatic model by Fiedler and Bukovski (2011), identified the high increase of precipitation rate in the areas where large wind farms are located which also gives a signal that human technogenic interference has an impact on the natural processes.

From the above results, the implications are that large scale wind farms gradually affect the atmosphere and might eventually become a reason of considerable climatic changes, so there is a sharp need to find the solution how to exploit the wind power without causing any

adverse effect to the environment and today the highly promising option available is installation of decentralized grid-connected and standalone systems in the form of micro-scale wind turbines (Tumalla et al., 2015).

Scientific and political institutions frequently underline the idea, that renewable energy systems bear the crucial role for the perspective sustainable global development. In such a context, wind energy is highly relevant as its utilization leads to carbon footprint reduction and opportunity to obtain the massive amount of energy (Bortolini, Gamberi, Graziani, Manzini & Pilati, 2013). It is important to notice, when the data concerning wind exploitation technologies' performance are being published, these figures mostly represent the performance of large scale projects, since the effectiveness of these systems has been practically proven in various settings and under different kinds of circumstances. Small wind turbines, however, do not usually draw as much attention as their large counterparts, although they are also able to cover significant electricity demand (Wood, 2011) and the data regarding the electric output of small wind turbines are usually not publicly available and to get the specific figures one should be entitled for the access to governmental energy and statistic institutions.

According to the World Wind Energy Association [WWEA] (2014) the industry involved in small wind turbine manufacturing has shown the 35 percent accumulated growth of newly installed energy capacity in the recent years and is expected to reach approximately 3 GW of the cumulative energy capacity generated by small-scale systems segment by 2020 (Fig. 1.3)

Fig. 1.3 SWT installed capacity world market forecast 2020.

Fig. 1.3. Adapted from “Small Wind World Report 2014” by World Wind Energy Association, 2014.

1.2 Research Objective and Relevance

The fast growth of energy consumption in Ireland, combined with the increasing depletion of domestic fossil fuels has resulted in a considerable raise in energy imports (European Renewable Energy Council, 2009). Ireland’s import dependence on fossil fuels reached 91 percent in 2006 making Ireland the most import dependent country in the EU (Howley, Ó Gallachóir & Dennehy, 2008). Heavy reliance on the exported fuel and the tendency to quick depletion of subsoil resources worldwide made an employment of renewable energy a significant concern for the country in order to satisfy future energy demand (Zhou, Lou, Li, Lu, & Yang, 2010). Furthermore, Ireland has an exceptionally rich wind energy resource endowment, which is four times as much as the European average (O’Rourke, Boyle, & Reynolds, 2009) and its estimated technical capacity is 613 TWh per annum of which the country currently utilizes 2.8 TWh meaning that Ireland exploits less than half a percent of its valuable indigenous asset (Sustainable Energy Ireland [SEI], 2004).

There is a range of important parameters which should be taken into account when energy resources are being evaluated. These parameters include stability of prices, geographical distribution of available resources, production shares, commercial status, reliability and level of environmental influence (O'Rourke et al., 2009). With regards to these factors, wind exploitation technologies look very promising and becoming more attractive to the consumers. Besides, renewable energy significantly reduces reliance on conventional fossil fuels, enhances security of supply, cuts down carbon dioxide emissions, delivering environmental benefits while creating jobs to the economy, thus contributing to the national development and welfare (Department of Communications, Energy and Natural Resources, 2012). Taking into consideration the aforementioned factors, on March 12th, 2007 the Department of Communications, Marine and Natural Resources published the White Paper, which outlined the key development strategies of the Government Energy Policy for 2007-2020 (European Renewable Energy Council, 2009). The primary goal of the accepted government strategy is to ensure competitive, reliable and sustainable energy for the economy and society, to decarbonize energy systems and diversify energy sources by reducing the reliance on conventional oil and gas fuels and reaching 40 percent of electricity consumption from renewable energy sources by 2020 (Clancy & Scheer, 2011).

Despite the seemingly smooth and promising plan, there is the number of significant challenges on the way to successful deployment of renewable energy technologies across the country which includes:

- the need for certainty and transparency in government regulations which will be able to support and encourage the long run interest in implementing renewable energy technologies among the customers;

- the need for cost effective and timely investments in the key strategic electricity transmission and distribution projects;
- ensuring the legal environment for renewable energy projects in the electricity market is appropriate, coherent and in accord with EU requirements;
- increasing public acceptance towards environmental and other impacts of the implemented renewable energy projects and securing potential benefits and elimination of any damage for local;
- modernization and expansion of the national electricity grid and energy infrastructure to support local economic development of the remote regions in Ireland (Department of Communications, Energy and Natural Resources, 2012).

On its way to reaching the target of covering up to 40 percent of national electricity demand by exploiting renewable energy technologies, Irish government has undertaken another resolute step towards development of renewable electricity generation by introducing the exported electricity tariff in 2009 (Goodbody, Walsh, McDonnell & Owende, 2012). This scheme was specifically designed to incentivize farms, business, households and other private users to employ renewable energy technologies by guaranteeing the support payment for each kWh of the surplus energy imported to the national grid (Irish Wind Energy Association [IWEA], 2009). The Irish feed-in tariffs became an important action which was supposed to lead to significant increase in number of householders implemented grid-connected micro-renewable electricity generation systems in their premises (Li, Reynolds, & Boyle, 2013).

Typical microgeneration technologies include wind turbines, solar photovoltaic, hydro power, and hybrid heat and power systems. At present time the installed capacity of small wind turbines in Ireland is constantly increasing (Fig. 1.4) and today this technology is capable of providing electricity not to isolated consumers only, but also partly cover the power demand of grid-connected households (International Energy Agency, 2006).

Table. 1.1 Current Installed Capacity for Micro generation in Ireland

Micro Generators	kW Installed Capacity	No. of Installations	Average Installation (kW)
Micro Wind	3984.86	763	5.22
Micro Photovoltaic	1203.788	375	3.21
Micro CHP	72.91	15	0.53
LPG Gas	1.2	1	1.2
Micro Hydro	61.85	13	4.76
Total	5324.608	1167	4.56

Table 1.1. Adapted from “Wind Microgeneration: Step by Step Guide” by Irish Wind Energy Association, 2014.

Although there is an abundance of wind resource in Ireland, the micro-scale wind technologies are not very popular to-date, the current situation on the Irish small-scale turbines market, however, demonstrates that small-scale wind exploitation devices are by far more demanded than any other renewable electricity generation home technologies (Li, Boyle & Reynolds, 2011), therefore the results obtained after conducting the research might be of high importance just as for private households owners to be able to obtain the data on the current economic viability of micro-renewable systems and to make an ultimate decision in favor of one or another energy system which will be optimal for certain individual case so for the manufacturer to have a broad overview of Irish wind energy exploitation technologies market, energy policy and wind resource characteristics to make further decision regarding possible market penetration strategy.

1.3 Research Object and Scope

The range of micro-scale wind turbines available on the Irish market, which can satisfy the needs of householders under certain settings, is quite broad (Li et al., 2011). In this study the cost effectiveness of the specific technology will be analyzed by comparing its performance

with the performance of the main field competitors which fall under the similar price range and technical specifications.

The usage name of the system under investigation is Energy Ball V200® and the design of this device is out of the frames of the classic horizontal axis three rotor blades micro-scale wind turbines what makes this technology unique for the Irish market of wind energy exploitation systems. The Energy Ball® V200 is an innovative technology developed by the Dutch company HomeEnergy. The device represents a spherical wind turbine with 5 rotor blades and a diameter of 1.98m (Fig. 1.5), which enables users to generate own electricity to partly cover energy needs. Due to its parameters and dimensions which meet European standards and requirements the Energy Ball® V200 can be installed in rural, urban and suburban areas (HomeEnergy, 2009).

Fig. 1.4. The System Energy Ball® V200.

Fig. 1.4. Adapted from “Energy Ball® V200 Wind Energy Presentation” by HomeEnergy, 2009.

In this paper the range of characteristics of small wind turbines which have the nominal annual average electricity output between 1500 and 2500 kWh on the assumption of the average

wind speed of 6-7 m/s and the capital cost in frames of €12 500 will be examined. At present time two systems which match the stated requirements are available on the Irish market: Ampair® 600 – 230V and Swift® 1.5 kW (Li et al., 2011). On the basis of the data regarding annual electricity output of the systems, capital cost, average household electrical load, imported and exported electricity price, bank loan rates, availability of the government grants, and the number of incentive years (Li et al., 2011), the economic viability of the systems will be assessed and the projections regarding cost effectiveness of the Energy Ball® V200 will be delivered.

Implications of the studies conducted by the IWEA (2014) demonstrate that many residential areas are not sufficiently suitable for wind turbines installation, because of buildings and trees which by creating turbulent air flows can substantially reduce efficiency and lifespan of wind exploitation device. The suggested ideal location is supposed to be on the top of a high tower which in its turn is situated on the hill with gentle slopes surrounded by countryside without any obstructions in the form of trees, houses or other buildings. In such conditions, the wind stream will be steady and laminar and the wind turbine will be able to utilize the largest amount of winds' kinetic energy and to eventually convert it into the highest electricity output possible (Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland [SEAI], 2013). Taking into account the aforementioned conditions, one can notice that micro-scale wind turbines are quite demanding in terms of location and can be mostly applied in well exposed sites in rural and suburban areas and according to the Central Statistics Office of Ireland (2012) the number of inhabitants dwelling in suitable locations is about 7 percent of total population of the country what gives us approximately 340 000 of potential technology consumers.

According to the Energy Efficiency and Conservation Authority [EECA] (2010) micro-scale wind turbines are already able to perform well at average annual wind speeds of about 4.5 m/s. Leaver, Pilbrow and Gardiner (2010), however, argue that a much higher average wind

speed of approximately 7 to 8 m/s is required to make the performance of micro-scale wind systems economically viable. According to the IWEA (2014) many, predominantly coastal and elevated regions in Ireland, have outstanding wind potential to fully realize the potential of micro-scale wind exploitation systems.

2. Literature Review

Constantly raising industrial scope and economic power worldwide inevitably leads to quick depletion of conventional fossil fuel resources. In order to meet future energy demand countries are gradually turning to the renewable energy sources such as biomass, solar, hydro, tidal, geothermal, wave and wind energy (O'Rourke et al., 2009). The last type of energy is one of the mostly utilized renewable energy sources nowadays. Due to excessive amount of the wind energy, large scale wind farms became the regular and reliable practice worldwide (Tummala et al., 2015). As has been proved, however, the large-scale wind exploitation projects have a significant adverse effect on the climatic conditions (Kaldellis & Zafirakis, 2011). The suitable option available, which is able to exploit energy of the wind without causing considerable natural changes, is decentralized systems of small scale wind turbines (Tumalla et al., 2015). In this chapter I am going to review the part of existing scientific literature regarding the nature of wind, wind energy, different types of small wind turbines, their distinctive features, and to convey the knowledge, ideas and opinions on the mentioned topics.

2.1 Renewable Energy

After the first oil shock in the early 70s the amount of wind technologies increased significantly (Bortolini et al., 2013). Among all the renewable energy sources available, wind met the most impressive growth worldwide in the 90s (Yuea, Liua, & Lioub, 2013). In that time, the range of European countries introduced important legal energy regulations with the

purpose to promote the installation of national grid-connected and standalone wind exploitation systems. Today, there are several countries, like the Netherlands, in which the energy market and wind power technologies became so largely integrated that the old incentive policies are being gradually abrogated, proving, that renewable energy sources can be a full-fledged substitute of the conventional energy sources based on fossil fuels combustion (WWEA, 2010).

The total power generating capacity worldwide was estimated at the rate of 5 360 GW in 2012 and more than 1 300 GW were covered by renewable energy resources, meaning that nonconventional energy sources are already able to meet up to 25 percent of the total world power demand (Renewable Energy Policy Network for the 21st Century, [REN 21] 2013). Wind turbines and solar photovoltaic panels accounted for 40 and 30 percent respectively of energy provided followed by hydropower which covers 25 percent of the global energy demand in renewable energy segment (REN 21, 2013). The data provided by the REN 21 demonstrate the stable tendency for wind energy exploitation technologies expansion in terms of total energy output.

Fig. 2.1 World wind power capacity 1996-2011.

Fig. 2.1. Adapted from “Renewables 2012: Global Status Report” by Renewable Energy Policy Network for the 21st Century, 2012.

When considering wind energy as a source of renewable energy, there is a range of advantages and disadvantages that need to be taken into account to obtain the best outcome from harnessing this particular type of renewable energy.

Advantages:

- Since wind energy is a source of power generated by the naturally flowing wind stream, it causes no pollution as wind turbines do not produce greenhouse emissions which have detrimental effect on the atmosphere.
- Wind power is a resource which can be utilized worldwide and is not bounded to the particular areas as traditional fossil fuels such as oil, coal and gas.
- The cost of wind energy utilization is one of the lowest-priced renewable energy technologies available today.
- Contemporary wind exploitation systems are available in large range of various sizes, designs and power outputs, therefore, can be used to generate electricity just as for small industrial utilities so for small towns and villages.
- Since wind turbines do not usually take up large space on the ground surface, the land in rural areas still may be used for agricultural needs (McHale, 2012).

Disadvantages:

- Due to its intermittent nature, wind strength may vary from a gentle breeze to a storm forced stream, therefore, the ultimate energy output entirely depends on the wind power, which might produce no energy in some specific days and generate an abundant output in the others.
- With the need to maximize potential of wind energy, the selected target sites might be located quite far from cities or industrial areas, therefore making the transfer of the

generated energy to adjacent electricity stations to bring additional expenditures often fairly substantial.

- While working wind turbines may cause noise pollution, which might have an adverse effect on the local inhabitants who live within the radius of the windmill.
- The landscape of areas where wind systems are erected undergoes significant visual changes (Wagner & Mathur, 2009).

2.2 Wind in Atmospheric Boundary Layers

Wind is created due to the difference of pressure levels in atmospheric layers and irregular heating of the Earth surface by the sun. The combination of these atmospheric phenomena results in stochastic motion within air layers. Wind characteristics are dependent on the altitude above the ground, terrain peculiarities, weather conditions and the cyclic Earth rotations. The wind patterns closer to the ground surface are very much changeable due to resistance created by roughness of the terrain, hills, trees and buildings. All these obstructions have the profound effect on the power and stability of the wind stream movement what makes the analysis of wind pattern quite a complicated matter (Wizelius, 2007).

Fig. 2.1 World wind power capacity 1996-2011.

Fig. 2.2. Adapted from “Annual Report 2013” by Hamon Group, 2013.

The wind profile varies in accordance with altitude and also with the amount and sort of obstacles towards which the wind stream moves. Smooth surfaces like ocean or flat terrain with no occlusions in the form of vegetation or buildings are capable of generating the best wind velocity at the lowest altitude. As has been already mentioned trees, hills and high building disturb the wind flow, shrink the speed and create a wind shear which in its turn may become a reason of additional hazard of turbulence which has a large detrimental effect of the wind turbine (Stankovic, Campbell & Harries, 2009). The figure 2.2 provided below demonstrates how the wind velocity alters with altitude over three different types of surface: smooth water (sea, ocean surface), a flat ground and forest.

Fig. 2.3. Wind speed as a function of altitude (height) above different surface features.

Fig. 2.3. Adapted from “Developing Wind Power Projects: Theory and Practice” by T. Wizelius, 2007, London: Routledge.

2.3 Energy of Wind

Wind energy exploitation systems are able to convert wind power into electricity by the rotation of turbine blades as wind stream passes over them (European Wind Energy Association [EWEA], 2009). As discussed above, the wind speed normally rises as the height above the

ground increases, therefore, wind turbines placed on a higher altitude are able to generate higher energy output than the corresponding wind systems installed at the same location but at a lower height. Wind turbines can also demonstrate best performance when the wind stream is able to approach rotor blades without being interrupted by any kind of obstructions. These obstacles can substantially slow down the velocity and cause turbulence which can result in reduction of system's performance and hasten deterioration of the turbine and its supporting structures. Furthermore, the intermittent nature of the wind heavily affects the energy output of the turbine. Since each wind exploitation system is entirely dependent on the availability of the wind power, other energy sources along with wind turbines should be also considered in case of wind stream absence. Even if the amount of wind power is generally sufficient for household needs, other energy sources should be readily available to adjust the voltage level within home circuit which might be affected by wind speed variance (Stankovic et al., 2007).

All the aforementioned facts demonstrate that urban environment makes the exploitation of wind systems highly challenging as it has a significant impact on the wind pattern, in contrast to rural areas which characteristics are much more technically suitable for wind turbine application. Thus, during the development of wind exploitation project in a single location one should take into account that there is a significant influence of environmental characteristics on the wind pattern and wind energy efficiency.

2.4 Wind Characteristics

Over the last years many researchers have been elaborating on an adequate statistical model to derive the wind distribution and direction frequency distribution functions. These statistical parameters of the main wind characteristics are of great importance not for technical and structural design analysis only but also for the wind energy exploitation performance evaluation and for the general wind energy potential forecast (Mathew, 2006).

According to Mathew (2006) to evaluate the perspective wind energy potential in a particular location, the wind data should be properly analyzed and interpreted. The inherently intermittent and geographically variable nature of wind can be substantially mitigated by accurate assessments (Leary, While & Howell, 2012). The data regarding wind pattern for making the preliminary energy forecast in specific area can be retrieved from meteorological stations located in proximity to the selected site and should be available for prolonged time spans in order to be extrapolated to the current wind conditions within the target site. The hourly wind speed data for an entire year at particular site are often unavailable or might be too expensive to purchase (Li et al., 2011). Furthermore, the analysis based on the data regarding wind speed variations in specific location collected within one year provides only 10 percent accuracy level for the future forecast (Mathew, 2006).

2.4.1 Wind Speed Characteristics

The most important criteria to determine a wind power potential in a target site is annual mean wind speed, measured in meters per second and annual wind speed distribution which reflects the proportion of time the wind stream blows at various speeds over the year (IWEA, 2014). Ten minutes mean wind speed is commonly used to make wind analysis as most software is set up to process the data over every ten minutes. The data then can be categorized on hourly, monthly and yearly basis (Mathew, 2006). The figure 2.5 illustrates the distribution of a wind velocity within target site on hourly basis.

Fig. 2.4 Wind speed distribution.

Fig. 2.4. Adapted from “Electricity Generation from Wind Power. Technology and Economics” by Electropaedia, 2013, www.mpoweruk.com/wind_power.htm

2.4.2 Wind Direction Characteristics

When installing a wind energy conversion system, the determination of wind direction is essential. In order to identify the wind direction wind vanes used to be mostly applied, today this task can be delegated to anemometers. Modern anemometers are able to measure the direction of the wind stream and wind velocity simultaneously. To carry out a full and accurate wind speed and direction analysis, the anemometer needs to be erected in the target site, ideally for a 12 month period at the turbine mast height (IWEA, 2014).

According to Mathew (2006) the data regarding both wind speed and stream direction can be illustrated in a combined way by applying wind rose. The wind rose is a diagram which helps visualize wind patterns in particular location. The chart can be divided into 8, 12 or 16 equally proportioned sectors indicating the wind from different directions. With help of wind rose chart two types of data can be obtained:

1. frequency expressed in percentage of time within which the wind is captured from a particular direction. By obtaining this sort of data one is able to identify the direction from which the most considerable amount of wind comes.
2. velocity with which wind blows in certain direction. This type of data serves to demonstrate the strength of the average wind spectra (Mathew, 2006).

Fig. 2.5 Wind roses indicating distribution of frequency and velocity of wind stream in different directions..

Fig. 2.5. Adapted from “Wind Rose Diagrams” by Autodesk Education Community, 2015, <http://sustainabilityworkshop.autodesk.com/buildings/wind-rose-diagrams>.

2.5 Wind Energy Technologies

2.5.1 Grid-connected Wind Energy Systems

Grid connected systems are those which directly connected to the electricity transmission and distribution systems. The decision to connect wind system to the electricity grid depends on the characteristics of the system to be used. Most large wind energy exploitation systems are designed in such a way to feed the surplus energy to the central national grid, however, different options might be also found, particularly in small scale wind technologies (Wagner & Mathur, 2009).

2.5.2 Standalone Wind Energy Systems

Standalone systems are those which are not directly connected to the national electricity grid. Such systems are mostly used to provide power to detached houses, farms and technical facilities located in remote areas. Examples can be remote telecommunication or water systems which require energy for water pumping with irrigation or drinking water supply aims. The power capacity of the wind turbines exploited in such conditions may vary between a few watts up to 50 kW (Ackermann & Söder, 2002). People living with direct access or close to the electricity transmission channels, however, might also become users of standalone wind energy systems. Such a decision can be made with the range of certain reasons in mind. To be more independent from the energy provided by the national electric power companies, some people might be willing to utilize renewable energy systems. By undertaking this step, they are able to considerably reduce their energy expenses, raise some funds by feeding surplus energy to the central power circuit and, besides, to demonstrate their support and dedication to sustainable clean energy resources (United States Department of Energy, 2013).

According to the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (1997) standalone wind exploitation systems can be beneficial on the assumption of:

- The annual average wind speed at the target area is not less than 4 m/s.
- The grid connections do not exist in the target locations or if it can be done with expansions associated with considerable expenses or if the cost of operations to integrate the power line to a remote area through the grid is unreasonable.
- Reduction of the environmental influence of electricity production based on fossil fuels combustion.

Depending on the size, standalone wind power systems can be divided into small-scale and large scale systems. Small-scale wind systems are mostly applied in rural and remote

locations nowadays. These machines are usually equipped with energy storage components to provide stable and reliable power stream. Small-scale wind exploitation devices can be more effective than extending the stationary electricity line to the national power grid. Large standalone wind systems are commonly exploited within urban areas, although the wind speed might be generally lower due to build up surroundings. Decisions to erect large scale wind systems in urban sites are usually made if wind pattern monitoring reveals sufficient wind resource within the certain area and environmental impact appears to be not highly significant (Stankovic et al., 2009).

Another issue concerning off-grid wind systems is consistency of energy supply. Leary et al. (2012) argues that consistency of supply is a critical factor which is determined by reliability (how often the system breaks down) and resilience (the speed at which the performance of the system restored). According to Piggot (2006) reliability is the biggest concern for micro-wind systems yet resilience is exceptionally important in remote sites where procurement of the spare parts can be highly complicated and time-consuming matter.

2.6 Wind Turbines

The power capacity of contemporary wind turbines can vary from a few hundred watts to a few Megawatts, like a 10 MW ST10 wind turbine recently developed by Norwegian turbine manufacturer SWAY illustrated on the Fig. 2.6 (SWAY, 2012). Traditionally, efficiency of the wind turbines is represented by their maximum energy output potential and this is also called as rated capacity of the wind turbine. Furthermore, the size of the wind turbine installed in certain area can be also explained as a function of cross sectional area, although most of the large scale wind turbines are predicted to reach their output power capacity at a wind speed of 13 m/s (Ferrigno, 2010).

In accordance with trends in wind turbines industry, in terms of the size and energy output turbines are usually categorized into several groups. Wind systems with a rated capacity of more than 1 MW fall under category of large wind turbines, systems with the capacity between 100 kW and 1 MW are within the group of medium wind turbines. Wind exploitation devices with the rated capacity less than 100 kW are known as small wind turbines. And the last category of micro-scale systems is represented by the turbines which electricity output does not exceed 10 kW (Sharman, 2009).

In line with Irish standards, the turbine is presumed to be free-standing, mast-mounted with horizontal axis design. The minimum requirement for the suitable installation area is supposed to be the location with an annual mean wind speed of 5 m/s with no adjacent occlusions (Energy Saving Trust, 2007).

Fig. 2.6 10 MW wind turbine developed by the SWAY Company (Norway).

Fig. 2.6. Adapted from: <http://www.swayturbine.no/?page=219&show=220>

2.6.1 Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines

Horizontal axis wind turbines are those whose moving shaft rotates horizontal to the ground (O'Rourke et al., 2009). The three bladed horizontal axis wind turbines are the most adopted technology nowadays (Bakshi & Dhasmana, 2015).

The horizontal axis wind turbines work when the wind blows creating a lifting force (Daly, 2011) which rotates the airfoil type rotor blades connected to the low-speed input shaft. The kinetic energy from the low-speed shaft is altered to quicker and more rational rotation speed by a gear box. The high-speed shaft then transmits its kinetic power to the generator which produces electricity. The yaw motor is integrated in system with the aim to adjust the position of the turbine in accordance with the direction of the blowing wind stream. Wind turbine controller (inverter) is necessary to convert the DC electricity generated by the turbine to AC electricity which is suitable for use in living premises (Greening & Azapagic, 2013). The efficiency of these turbines heavily depends on strong and steady wind stream, therefore, they are primarily installed at altitudes higher than vertical axis wind turbines (Tummala et al. 2015).

Fig. 2.7 Components of a typical horizontal axis wind turbine.

Fig. 2.7. Adapted from “Wind Power: A Renewable Energy Strategy for Ireland” by K. Daly, 2011, EE535 Renewable Energy Systems, Technology & Economics, <https://sites.google.com/site/ee535test/keith-daly>

Large-scale turbines are always connected to the central grid and generate energy to cover regional or national power demand. Small and micro-scale wind technologies are often used as a supplement to the conventional grid-delivered energy and in case if surplus energy is available it can be either stored in power accumulating batteries or feed back to the grid with help of specially tuned equipment (Moriarty, 2010).

Horizontal axis wind turbines can demonstrate significantly lesser performance if put into turbulent or low wind settings. Since these wind turbines are very sensitive to wind speed, density and direction, it is strongly recommended to always position horizontal axis wind turbines in accordance with wind stream direction in order to obtain the maximum energy output (Moriarty, 2010).

In addition to the difficulty of operating within turbulent or weak airflow, small-scale wind turbines are subjected to the problem connected with starting the whole rotor system at

low wind speed. Since majority of the HAWTs are not equipped with variable pitch blades, the angle of wind attack might not coincide with the low rotational speed of the rotor. This discrepancy might become a cause of the considerable delay in the rotor's initial acceleration (Ebert & Wood, 1997). The field study conducted by Wright and Wood (2004) demonstrated that three bladed, 2m diameter horizontal axis wind turbine starts rotating at the wind speed of 4.6 m/s, which supports the assumption that micro-scale wind exploitation systems installed within areas with the average annual wind speed lower than 4 m/s are hardly to reach their optimal output level.

2.6.2 Vertical Axis Wind Turbines

Vertical axis wind turbines are those whose rotating shaft is in vertical position relative to the ground (O'Rourke et al., 2009). VAWTs are mostly developed for the needs of urban deployment, as this type of turbines is not wind direction dependent unlike horizontal axis wind turbines which are subjected to the negative effect caused by changes in wind stream direction. As a result there is no need for the yaw mechanism to adjust the wind turbine position into the wind direction. Furthermore, since shafts, the generator and the gearbox are located on the ground, service and maintenance are much easier. Nevertheless, these turbines remain less attractive to the customers since their efficiency considerably yields to the electricity output of HAWTs (Cace, Horst & Syngellakis, 2007).

Most of the VAWTs designs are grouped as the Darrieus and Savonius types depending on the principles used to capture the blowing wind (Daly, 2009). Savonius wind turbines have 'S' shaped cross section when looked from above and their rotational speed is always lesser than the wind velocity because of the drag, which in its turn decreases the efficiency of the turbine (Cace et al., 2007). The Darrieus wind turbines consist of a number of straight or curved airfoil blades mounted on the vertical shaft or framework. These turbines function due to the

lifting forces generated during rotation and such a design makes the blades rotate faster than the wind speed (Tummala et al., 2015).

The table 2.1 outlines main turbine categories by comparing advantages and disadvantages of each group.

Table 2.1 Comparison of horizontal axis and vertical axis wind turbines.

Turbine type	Advantages	Disadvantages
Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines	Efficient	Noise
	Proven to work	Not Efficient when wind Frequently changes
	Widely used	Creates Vibrations
	Most economic	Visually unappealing
	Many products available	
Vertical Axis Wind Turbines	Less sensitive to turbulence	Not yet proven
	Wind direction immaterial	Less efficient
	Silent	Fewer models available
	Easier to install and maintain	Fewer working examples
	Fewer Vibrations	

Table 2.1. Adapted from “Implementation of Urban Wind Turbines in the Meuse Rhine Harbor” by F. Dekkers, Y. Staal, & L. Teunissen, 2009, Wineur Wind Cities Network Meeting.

Paul Gipe (2004), one of the American leading scientists on wind energy, argues that micro-scale wind turbines are very unlikely to deliver more than 30 percent of wind energy for any considerable period of time. Moreover, micro-scale wind turbines have certain technical limitations. According to Irish regulations, the total height of the device including the mast shall not exceed 13 m (Li et al., 2012), but at aptitude of 10-12 meters above the ground the wind power is only 65-75 percent of the power available at the height of 50 meters (Piggot, 2006). Most wind turbines are usually installed too close to the ground or even on the roofs, but, according to Piggot (2006), the greater the unevenness of the landscape, the more obstacles

around the turbine, the greater the reduction of the available wind resource and an ultimate energy output can be shrank up to 90 percent.

According to Ledo, Kosasih and Cooper (2011) the factors which can substantially reduce the energy output are intermittent wind speed and high turbulence due to build up surroundings within urban areas. These factors become main reasons of variable cyclic loads that make the wind turbine vital parts particularly susceptible and ultimately fail due to fatigue (Leary et al., 2012).

2.7 Environmental Impact

Many discussions have been revolving around the environmental impact caused by wind turbines and governmental attempts to turn Ireland into industrialized green energy zone have certain detrimental environmental consequences.

Environmental impact due to visual and noise pollution is considered substantially higher as the similar effect caused by exploitation of conventional fossil fuels. The effect of wind turbines on birds, animals, land use, public safety, aviation, archeology and landscape change is also being considered.

As has been mentioned, the main concern for wind turbines still remains the visual and sound pollution (Gipe, 2004) as a consequence, more than one hundred opposition groups against deployment of new wind projects were set up across Ireland (BBC News, 2014). Such a situation has awoken the wave of protest across the country against installation of wind turbines. On January 6 and April 15, 2014 thousands of protesters from across the country took part in a demonstration in Wexford and in Dublin against the erection of wind farms in Ireland because of adverse effect they cause to landscape, animals, environment and people's health (The Irish Times, 2014).

These issues, however, usually mainly relate to large scale projects and no research so far has identified the exceptionally adverse effect of micro-scale wind systems on birds, for example (Reuther & Thull, 2011).

According to Bloch (2011), however, environmental impact can be significantly mitigated by proper installation of wind systems in areas with less sensitive surroundings, besides, since wind turbines have no carbon footprint while generating electricity, wind systems are considered free of carbon emissions (Stankovic et al., 2009).

Studies conducted by the EECA (2004) demonstrate that the noise produced by wind turbine is an inevitable attribute accompanying wind turbine's performance. According to EECA (2004) the sound becomes somewhat disturbing only when the wind speed is high and since turbines are usually operate in quite calm wind settings and very occasionally got into critical circumstances, the disturbance due to wind turbine noise is somewhat inflated issue. Gipe (2004) however argues that even though the noise produced by wind turbines might be not substantial it is generally audible to some extent and mostly perceived as annoying and unpleasant.

3. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

In the previous part, various scientific sources regarding wind and wind exploitation systems were reviewed. All the knowledge and opinions presented concern concepts such as nature of wind, wind power, and wind turbines. These ideas, however, mostly relate to the essentials of the renewable energy utilization technologies and industry in general. In the following part the much deeper concepts including mathematical, statistical and economic models are to be explored. These concepts are of high importance for the further analysis therefore they need to be carefully elaborated in order to resolve the stated issue and deliver solid conclusions.

3.1 Statistical Models for Wind Data Analysis

In order to obtain a suitable and reliable statistical distribution model which will be able to let retrieve the data regarding wind regimes and wind patterns for making further forecasts, various probability functions were applied during the case studies. Ultimately, Weibull and Rayleigh distributions were found to be those methods which are able to deliver the most accurate outcomes regarding the wind patterns and variations in target sites (Manwell, McGowan & Rogers, 2009). Tuller and Brett (1984) in their turn argue, that from a practical standpoint, among these two approaches, Weibull distribution method is more advisable and its selection can be credited due to its flexibility and relative simplicity in application, as it requires only two parameters to estimate wind speed distribution: the shape factor k and the scale factor c (Wizelius, 2007), unlike the Rayleigh function, which is a special case of Weibull distribution and is more cumbersome and complex in use.

Average Wind Speed

The average wind velocity (V_m) is among the vital parameters on the wind pattern at a target location (Mathew, 2006). It can be calculated with the following equation:

$$V_m = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n V_i \quad \text{Eq. 3.1}$$

Where:

V – velocity of the wind stream (m/s);

n – number of received results.

For the ultimate wind power calculations, however, the results obtained by applying the equation 3.1 might be somewhat misleading (Mathew, 2006). Since the sum of the average wind speeds for the certain period cubed $(V_1 + V_2 + V_3 + \dots + V_n)^3$ and the sum of cubes of the each wind velocity $(V_1^3 + V_2^3 + V_3^3 + \dots + V_n^3)$ is not equal, these calculations might provide

the wrong numbers with respect to the power potential of the wind. Therefore, for the calculations of the mean wind energy, the velocity should be weighted for its power content by applying the following equation (Wizelius, 2007):

$$V_m = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n V_i^3 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad \text{Eq. 3.2}$$

Frequency Distribution

In order to compute the power density of the wind at a particular site it is not sufficient to have the data on average wind velocity only. It is also important to possess the data on different wind speeds and their duration that occur within the target area. Both these concepts combined are called the frequency distribution of the wind speed (Wizelius, 2007).

For obtaining the most accurate statistical results, it is highly recommended to carry out wind measurements during the period of more than several years. If to plot the number of hours in every interval against wind speed then the frequency distribution will take a form of a histogram. According to the shape of the distribution diagram one can get an insight regarding the behavior of wind regimes, like steady wind stream which has a nearly symmetrical frequency distribution (also called Gauss distribution) whereas unsteady wind regimes might have an asymmetrical distribution which usually refers to the name of Weibull distribution function (Meel & Smulders, 1989). Before explaining each of this function, there are two more important statistical parameters, which need to be covered.

Standard Deviation

Standard deviation (σ_V) is one of the statistical instruments to measure the inconsistency of wind speeds within a particular range of results on wind observations. This

parameter provides the data on how the individual velocities deviate from the average value (Mathew, 2006). The results can be derived with the following equation:

$$\sigma_v = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (V_i - V_m)^2}{n}} \quad \text{Eq. 3.5}$$

The lower the value of σ_v the higher the consistency of the given data set.

Gaussian (Normal) Distribution

The wind velocity V is distributed as the Gaussian (Normal) distribution if its probability density function is the following:

$$f(V) = \left(\frac{1}{(\sigma_v \sqrt{2\pi})} \right) \exp \left[-\frac{(V - V_m)^2}{2\sigma_v^2} \right] \quad \text{Eq. 3.6}$$

Where:

V_m – Mean wind velocity;

σ – Standard deviation.

Weibull Distribution

The wind speed which is measured at a target location tends to commonly adhere to the Weibull probability distribution function, which is a widespread technique to describe wind pattern and potential wind energy (Cabello & Orza, 2010). This type of distribution is named after the Swedish scientist Waloddi Weibull, who first described in details and presented this statistical approach to the scientific community in 1951. Today the Weibull distribution is a very popular instrument due to its versatility, relative simplicity, and ability to assume the characteristics of many various types of distributions in many spheres (Rinne, 2008).

Particularly in the case of wind energy, Weibull probability distribution is usually characterized by the shape and scale factors depicted on the diagram. This technique is commonly applied in wind speed measurements because of certain properties it has. The most

important feature is that Weibull distribution's threshold factor does not utilize the negative values and is able to provide the data over the large range of wind speeds (Acosta & Djokic, 2010).

The shape of the Weibull distribution curve is determined by the scale factor. The power of the wind, however, varies in accordance with the cubic power of the wind velocity.

Wind speed variations can be expressed with two Weibull distribution functions:

1. The probability density function ($f(V)$) demonstrates the probability for the given wind velocity (V) to occur within certain fraction of time (Mathew, 2006):

$$f(V) = \frac{k}{c} \left(\frac{V}{c}\right)^{k-1} e^{-\left(\frac{V}{c}\right)^k} \quad \text{Eq. 3.6}$$

Where:

k – Weibull shape factor

c – Weibull scale factor

2. The cumulative density function of a wind velocity (V) is used to estimate if the current wind speed is equal, higher or lower than the average wind speed within the certain time period. Since the CDF represents the integral of the PDF, it is expressed by the following equation (Manwell et al., 2009):

$$F(V) = \int_0^{\infty} f(V)dV = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{V}{c}\right)^k} \quad \text{Eq. 3.7}$$

Therefore, the probability for the current wind speed of being between the wind velocities V_1 and V_2 can be derived by computing the difference between these previously calculated cumulative probabilities and each of them corresponds to certain wind velocity (V_1 and V_2)(Mathew, 2006). That is:

$$P(V_1 < V < V_2) = F(V_2) - F(V_1) \quad \text{Eq. 3.8}$$

According to Mathew (2006) the uniformity of the wind under Weibull distribution is determined by the shape k factor. The effect of the k factor on the probability density and cumulative distribution functions of the wind is demonstrated on the Fig 3.1 and 3.2.

On the both figures one can see the scale factor (c) which represents the wind speed and is equal to 9.8 m/s, and the shape factor (k), which determines the profile of the distribution, and is from 1.5 to 4.

The chart 3.1 represents how the probability density function of the wind speeds at particular sites changes with k factor.

Fig. 3.1 Weibull probability density functions for different shape factors.

Fig. 3.1. Adapted from “Wind Energy: Fundamentals, Resource Analysis and Economics” by S. Mathew, 2006, Luxemburg: Springer Science+Business Media.

The chart 3.2 demonstrates how the cumulative frequency function of the wind speeds at particular sites changes with k factor.

Fig. 3.2 Weibull cumulative frequency functions for different shape factors.

Fig. 3.2. Adapted from “Wind Energy: Fundamentals, Resource Analysis and Economics” by S. Mathew, 2006, Luxembourg: Springer Science+Business Media.

3.2 Power Available in Wind

In order to evaluate the power which can be potentially extracted from the wind stream, the range of mathematic formulas and relationships exist (Jain, 2010).

The basic formula for calculating the kinetic energy of an air flow with a given mass (m) and velocity (V) is:

$$KE = \frac{1}{2}mV^2 \quad \text{Eq. 3.9}$$

In order to obtain the data regarding the kinetic energy of wind stream available for the wind turbine, the data on the density of streaming airflow and the volume of an air mass captured by the rotor blades should be available:

$$KE = \frac{1}{2}\rho_{\alpha}vV^3 \quad \text{Eq. 3.10}$$

Where:

KE – kinetic energy (measured in Joules);

ρ_{α} – density of streaming (normally is considered to be 1.225 kg/m^3 above sea level at 15°C) (Wizelius, 2007);

v – volume of the air mass flowing against the rotor blades of the turbine (measured in m^3);

V – wind velocity (m/s).

To calculate the kinetic energy for the particular wind turbine, the data on the swept area of the blades exposed to the stream (Fig. 3.3) should be first obtained. Once this data are retrieved, we can substitute the parameter which refers to the volume of the air mass flowing against the rotor blades (v) to the number which stands for the rotor area exposed to the wind flow (A) and the ultimate equation is the following (Mathew, 2006):

$$P = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{\alpha} A V^3 \quad \text{Eq. 3.11}$$

Fig. 3.3 demonstrates the swept area exposed to the wind stream with help of two and three dimensional views of the turbine:

Fig. 3.3 A wind stream with velocity (V) passes through the swept area of the turbine's blades (A).

Fig. 3.3. Adapted from: “Coherent Application Threads” by Boston University, <http://people.bu.edu/dew11/windasenergy.html>

3.3 Wind Turbine Power

The actual energy generated by the turbine fully depends on the capability of the blades to harvest the wind stream and is defined through the estimation of the amount of kinetic power captured by the rotor blades and transferred to the convertor. This amount is usually called the power coefficient (C_p) and can be expressed by the following formula (Mathew, 2006):

$$P_T = \frac{1}{2} C_p \rho_\alpha A V^3 \quad \text{Eq. 3.13}$$

The wind energy equation cited above demonstrates that the amount of energy content in the wind stream will vary in accordance with alterations of the wind speed and if the wind speed doubles, the forecasted wind power will be approximately eight times as much as the previously calculated wind energy on the basis of the previously derived number regarding the wind speed (Gipe, 2004). For example, if the first wind speed measured is equal to 4 m/s, then the predicted power output will be 64 watts ($4^3 = 64$) and if the wind speed doubles by 8 m/s the forecasted energy available in the wind increases accordingly by 512 watts ($8^3 = 512$) that gives the difference by eight times between the obtained numbers. Since the wind power is a cubic function of the wind velocity, a 10 percent increase of wind speed may ultimately result in 37 percent of power available in the air flow making wind power entirely dependent on its speed and making wind speed a crucial factor for the amount of the perspective electricity generation (Gipe, 2004).

The performance of wind turbines is usually described by the power curve, which represents the energy output of the turbine over a range of wind speeds (Walker, 2011). The cut-in, rated and cut-out wind speeds are among the most significant parameters which determine the power curve of the turbine (Wizelius, 2007).

The minimum wind velocity that can make wind blades rotate and the wind system produce usable power is known as cut-in speed and is typically between 3 m/s and 4 m/s.

As wind speed tends to increase starting from the cut-in speed to the rated speed, the power output of the turbine increases accordingly. The rated speed is the parameter which represents the wind speed that the system can produce its rated output. The rated power output of turbine, however, is usually limited by the rated speed which is usually between 12 m/s and 15 m/s and obtaining of the extra power when the wind speed is over rated is very unlikely due to limited capacity of the micro-scale systems electrical generator (Gipe, 2009).

When wind speed keeps increasing at one point it reaches the so called cut-out speed which means the wind velocity that a wind turbine employs a breaking system, stops the rotation of the blades and ceases electricity generation in order to prevent any damage to the rotor. Typically the cut-out wind speed is 17 m/s for the micro-scale systems available in Ireland (Li et al., 2011).

Fig. 3.4 Variation of the power output depending on the steadiness of the wind speed.

Fig. 3.4. Adapted from: “Wind Farm Noise Statutory Nuisance Complaint Methodology” by AECOM, 2011, London.

3.4 Wind Turbine Performance

Let us now have a closer look at the two key parameters according to which performance of the wind exploitation systems is typically evaluated.

Annual Energy Production

Since the power curve method is proved to deliver the most realistic results regarding energy output of wind turbines, this technique can be applied for obtaining the data on the annual energy production (*AEP*) for the particular wind system at the specific target location (Gipe, 2004). For this purpose the wind speed frequency distribution function will be used to evaluate the *AEP*. It will be computed by multiplying the output power produced by the wind turbine at each measured wind velocity interval with the certain amount of hours within each interval by applying the following equation:

$$AEP = T \int_{V_{ci}}^{V_{co}} P_T(v) f(v) dv \quad \text{Eq. 3.14}$$

Where:

T – the number of hours in a year which is equal to 8760;

P_T – power of the turbine at a speed of V ;

V_{co} and V_{ci} cut-out and cut-in wind velocities respectively.

Capacity Factor

For obtaining the data on the potential field performance of wind systems there is one more parameter exists which is defined as the ratio of the actual energy produced to the energy that could have potentially been generated, if the turbine would have been operating at its rated power throughout the certain time span. This metrics is known as the capacity factor (C_F) and it is usually expressed on annual basis by applying the following formula:

$$C_F = \frac{AEP}{P_R T} \quad \text{Eq. 3.13}$$

Where:

P_R – rated power of the wind system;

T – the number of hours in a year (8760 hours).

Mathew (2006) argues that a capacity factor of the reasonably efficient wind system at a target site may vary from 0.25 to 0.4. If the capacity factor of the turbine exceeds the 0.4 it indicates that this systems performs exceptionally well at a given wind regime.

3.5 Turbine Efficiency

As has been previously discussed wind turbines are designed in a way to be able to utilize the highest amount of the energy available in the wind. This power, however, cannot be fully extracted even by the most advanced contemporary wind systems and some of the unutilized energy simply passes over the blades. To convert the entire amount of the kinetic energy available in the wind stream into mechanic energy would mean that the velocity of the air mass behind the rotor blades must fall to zero, which is physically impossible since it deviates from the flow continuity principle (Bukala, Damaziak, Kroszczyński, Krzeszowiec & Malachowski, 2015).

The relationships which describe the theoretical maximum efficiency of the wind of such energy conversion were derived in a range of studies conducted between 1922 and 1925 by the German physicist Albert Betz. By applying the principle of flow continuity and wind energy difference in front and behind the turbine, Albert Betz managed to demonstrate that the efficiency of the theoretically ideal turbine entirely depends on the relative upstream and downstream speeds of the wind stream. Furthermore, he has proven that the optimal ratio between the velocities exists (Mohamed, 2011):

$$\frac{V_1}{V_2} = \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{Eq. 3.12}$$

Where:

V_1 – wind speed in front of the turbine;

V_2 – wind speed behind the turbine.

According to Betz, the maximum possible aerodynamic efficiency of any wind turbine with horizontal axis of rotation is equal to 59.3 percent (Mohamed, 2011) and this parameter was named the Betz limit.

Real wind systems are also subjected to the to the energy outflows associated with the friction losses on the blades surface, blade tip losses due to the air pressure equalization and the formation of turbulent flows behind the rotor. Furthermore, the ultimate efficiency of the turbine might be further deteriorated by the number of losses due to electrical and mechanical reasons (Bukala et al., 2015). Today the most state-of-the-art high power wind exploitation systems which are commercially available on the market can achieve the highest efficient level (coefficient of performance) of 45 percent (ABB Group, 2011), whereas even the most advanced and well-designed micro-scale wind solutions can reach the top productivity level of 35 percent (Wind Power Program, 2014) on the assumption of the most favorable weather conditions. Depending on many variables such as the design and configuration of the rotor blades, hub height, weather settings, position of the wind turbine and other on- and off-site factors (Hemami, 2011), the average performance coefficient among micro-scale wind turbines usually falls within the range between 15 and 25 percent (Bukala et al., 2015).

Fig. 3.5 The power curve of the wind system Siemens 1300 as a function of wind velocity.

Fig. 3.5. Adapted from “Developing Wind Power Projects: Theory and Practice” by T. Wizelius, 2007, London: Routledge.

4. Research Design and Method

4.1 Research Design

According to Vaus (2001) research design refers to the entire strategy that the researcher chooses to integrate the different components of the study in a consistent and logical way, thereby, ensuring that the research problem will be effectively addressed. The function of a research design is to ensure that the evidences obtained enable the researcher to effectively address the research problem as logically and unambiguously as possible (Vaus, 2001). Since the question of the study concerns cost effectiveness of micro-scale wind turbines and the main objective is to identify economic viability of the certain technology under specific circumstances, this research will be carried out by applying a case study framework.

Case study approach is often used to narrow down a broad field of research with one or few easily researchable examples (Anastas, 1995) and the emphasis of the case-based research

typically tends to be upon an intensive examination of the settings under which the cases fall (Bryman, 2008). In order to carry out the aforementioned approach the picture of an issue needs to be obtained by comparing the data sets on the technical and economic performance of the existing technologies (cases) under different circumstances which correspond to the determined sample with the data on the technology under investigation.

4.2 Research Method

Since the research is entirely based on the numerical data provided by the official governmental and statistical institutions of Ireland, by wind turbine manufacturers and distributors, as well as the numerical data obtained by applying the optimization software described below, the method of the study is quantitative.

The economic and technical estimation of renewable energy exploitation systems can be performed in a number of different ways with various degrees of approximation (Simic, 2012). In case of this particular study the first step which includes obtaining the numbers regarding average wind speed and average electrical load which are crucial for further calculations will be performed by applying simulation software HOMER which provides artificial, but statistically reasonable results. The economic analysis of the wind systems will be carried out by using the Discounted Cash Flow and Payback methods. The descriptions of the technical capabilities of the software and the financial formulas are adduced below.

4.2.1 Hybrid Optimization Model for Electric Renewables

In order to identify the optimal settings for implementation of the micro-renewable system in Ireland, it is necessary to consider each particular region and its locally-available resources as well as seasonal changes in electricity demand and consumption. This can be

fulfilled by applying the Hybrid Optimization Model for Electric Renewables (HOMER) (Goodbody et al., 2012).

HOMER is a simulation and optimization software tool developed by the US National Renewable Energy Laboratory (Hamad & Aslaad, 2010). This software contains a range of renewable energy components models and is capable of estimating the appropriate technological options based on the cost and availability of resource in the target location (Khan, & Iqbal, 2005). The HOMER optimization model significantly simplifies the estimation process of both off- and on-grid power systems by simulating hourly energy balance calculations (Simic et al., 2012).

HOMER was developed with the purpose to overcome the challenges of intermittency, unpredictability and seasonality associated with renewable energy sources and became a widely used software due to its ability to examine the particular electricity sector as a single entity which makes HOMER a powerful tool for building the accurate models of the energy demand profiles in various locations, in this case, in Ireland i.e. to evaluate the electricity demand of the country where on-site fossil fuels-based energy systems are the most popular energy providers, and in which only 0.2 percent of the transport energy demand was covered by electrical energy (Howley, Dennehy, Holland & Ó Gallachóir, 2011).

Specifications of the system components are inputted in the software together with the data on the renewable energy resource available in particular location. HOMER works on the basis of 8 760 hours of the operational year which can be inserted as a real data or computed by the HOMER using the average data to identify loading and energy resources. The software is able to determine, on an hourly basis, if the ultimate output from the renewable energy system is sufficient to meet the energy load at a particular hour (Goodbody, 2012). If there is a lack of renewable energy resource at particular site, HOMER is able to supplement the power obtained

from renewable resources with the energy received from auxiliary energy sources such as diesel generator or national electricity grid (Türkyay & Telli, 2011).

The important question is the maximization of energy production with smallest energy cost. The cost optimization in HOMER is fulfilled on an economic basis in terms of the lowest Total Net Present Cost (TNPC), which refers to the life cycle of the system and encompasses all components of the system over the entire lifespan (Lambert, 2006). HOMER carries out the energy and cost balance computations for every system configuration under investigation. The software then determines whether the certain configuration is feasible, i.e. whether it can cover the electric demand at the certain location under the specific conditions, and also evaluates the amount of expenses associated with the installation and operation of the system over its entire lifetime. The system cost calculations account for costs such as capital, replacement, operation and maintenance, as well as fuel and interest rate (Simic et al., 2012). The optimum micro-renewable energy project from the technical standpoint is the one which is able to meet the particular energy load under the specific user constraints with the lowest NPC (Lambert, 2006).

HOMER is also able to calculate the CO₂ emissions produced by the system based on carbon content of the fuels and the properties of the exploited equipment. The number is based on the one operational year of every system with CO₂ emissions outputted by the model as kg CO₂ yr⁻¹. Where the renewable energy option is coupled with a non-renewable option, a negative value for emissions can be returned if a large amount of low-emissions power from the renewable energy sources is feed back to the national electricity grid due to low-emissions power displacing high emissions power (Lambert, 2006).

4.2.2 Economic Considerations

The parameters and equations mentioned in the Theory chapter are widely applied for deriving the data on wind patterns in order to analyze wind resource in the potential target

locations and to make future forecasts and decisions in favor or against the installation of certain wind system. All these techniques, however, are mostly used by engineers and technicians and might be somewhat complex and incomprehensible for the average people. Needless to say, however, that in the list of the factors for making the ultimate decision to either have the system installed or to keep using conventional gas and oil resources, the cost effectiveness is among the key ones. Cost effectiveness of small wind turbines still demonstrates uncertainty and remains the subject of discussion for recent years, and the main question is if micro-scale turbines are able to considerably contribute to reduction of the annual electricity expenses or they are just trendy green accessories?

The range of economic approaches for making analysis on cost effectiveness of wind turbines exists which might assist in determining the financial attractiveness of such investments including Annuity method, Cash Flow analysis, Discounted Cash Flow (Net Present Value) approach, and Payback method (Wizelius, 2007).

In this study to answer the research question ‘Is Energy Ball® V200 more cost effective than classic horizontal axis three rotor blades micro-scale wind turbines in the setting of Irish household?’ the Discounted Cash Flow and the Payback method will be applied.

Discounted Cash Flow Method

Among the most widespread approaches for making forecasts on investment projects is the Discounted Cash Flow method (DCF) (Khatib, 2003). This technique proved to be a reliable indicator of project’s economic attractiveness since it provides the insight into the value of the project based upon the present value of the cash flows that the project is expected to generate in the future (cash in- and outflows) and is used to carry out a cost/benefit comparison for identifying the optimal investment option during the overall assessment procedure (Eschenbach, 2010). In frames of wind energy and wind technologies, cash inflows result from

money saved by substituting energy provided by the national energy authorities to energy generated by own power producing system and electricity exported to the national grid and consequently sold, and cash outflows are represented by initial investment outlays and operating expenses (Gass, Strauss, Schmidt & Schmid, 2011) which mainly represent maintenance costs, land lease, work force related expenditures, insurance, etc. (Blanco, 2009).

Economic attractiveness of an investment in a certain project associated with wind energy is usually evaluated according to its Net Present Value (Voivontas, Assimacopoulos & Mourelatos, 1998). Investors are typically concerned with the maximum NPV for a preferred discount rate of future cash flows. Cash in- and outflows are discounted to reflect the risk and time preferences of the investor associated with the perspective cash flows. The DCF method usually consists of the following steps:

- evaluating the future cash flows for the certain range of the discrete time periods;
- discounting these cash inflows to the present value of money at a specific rate of return on the investment that reflects the relative risk of achieving the cash flows and the time value of money.

A project can be claimed economically attractive in case if its Net Present Value is equal to or higher than zero. The higher the NPV the more lucrative the project is. This relation is expressed by the following equation (Brigham & Erhardt, 2011):

$$\begin{aligned} NPV &= (CF)_0 + \frac{CF_1}{(1+i)^1} + \frac{CF_2}{(1+i)^2} + \dots + \frac{CF_n}{(1+i)^n} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^n \frac{CF_n}{(1+i)^n} \end{aligned} \tag{Eq. 4.1}$$

Where:

n – lifespan of the wind system expressed in number of years;

i – actual interest rate offered by the financial intuition on the provided loan;

CF_0 – initial investment which constitutes the capital cost of the system plus any related expenses. This value is always negative therefore is expressed either in brackets or with the negative sign;

CF – cash flow in the corresponding year (Khatib, 2003) which in its turn can be calculated by applying the following equation:

$$CF = S + P - M \quad \text{Eq. 4.2}$$

Where:

S – funds saved due to replacing the imported electricity;

P – revenue generated by exporting the surplus energy to the grid;

M – annual maintenance costs (Li et al., 2013).

Payback Period Method

The payback period of investment is typically applied to evaluate the economic feasibility of the project on the basis of years required to recover the funds invested in a project (Brigham & Erhardt, 2011), in the given case the viability of micro-scale wind solutions is an important factor for making an ultimate decision in favor or against the certain system (Daniels, 2012). Payback period (n) is expressed in number of years necessary for covering the invested amount of funds. This metrics can be derived by using the following equation (Brigham & Erhardt, 2011):

$$n = \text{Number of years prior to full recovery} + \frac{\text{Unrecovered cost at start of the year}}{\text{Cash flow during full recovery year}} \quad \text{Eq. 4.3}$$

The aforementioned equation is usually applied when cash flows expected in upcoming years are uneven. In this study, however, the calculations will be made on the assumption of the equal cash inflows, therefore, the payback can be calculated by applying a slightly simplified equation, which is:

$$n = \frac{\textit{Initial Investment}}{\textit{Cash Inflow per Period}} \quad \text{Eq. 4.4}$$

The payback method, however, has couple of flaws. First, cash inflows generated in different years are all given the same weight, meaning, the time value of money is not taken into consideration. Second, unlike NPV, which tells investors how much wealth a certain project brings, the payback only gives the number of years required to recover the investment (Brigham & Ehrhardt, 2011). For the average consumer, however, this number might have a significant value since it is able to give a relatively precise answer on the question of how much time will pass before the initial investment is recovered.

Both methods were applied for identifying cost effectiveness of photovoltaic panels in studies conducted by Li, Reynolds and Boyle across Ireland, in studies on economic viability of micro-scale wind solutions in Austria conducted by Gass, Strauss, Schmidt and Schmid, in as well as in the performance and viability analysis of small wind turbines in European Union carried out by Bortolini, Gamberi, Graziani, Manzini and Pilati.

4.3 Object of Analysis

As a unit of analysis for this study, the households located in rural areas in Ireland will be selected. In order to narrow down this huge area of investigation, the particular units of observation will be micro-scale privately owned wind turbines and households located in well exposed sites (average wind velocity ≥ 5.5 m/s) in rural areas of Ireland with the average annual electrical load of approximately 5 500 kWh.

4.3.1 Renewable Resource Availability in Ireland

Ireland is a relatively small country which experiences considerable variations of resources availability in different regions. According to Goodbody et al. (2012), in order to

evaluate the most suitable energy system for each region, it is necessary to split the entire area of the state into the localised sites on the base of locally-available renewable power sources.

Ireland was consequently divided into eight regions: Northwest, West, Southwest, South, Southeast, East, Midlands North, and Midlands South (Fig. 4.1). The assumed boundaries were designed to differentiate between the regions with certain resources available and to build a benchmark upon which to estimate the feasibility of every renewable resource in each assumed region. Table 4.1 represents the key renewable and non-renewable power resources available in each presumed region.

Fig. 4.1 Regional boundaries presumed for modelling a decentralized energy network in Ireland.

Fig. 4.1. Adapted from “Regional integration of renewable energy systems in Ireland – The role of hybrid energy systems for small communities” by C. Goodbody, E. Walsh, K. McDonnell, & P. Owende, 2012, Electrical Power and Energy Systems.

Table 4.1 Key renewable and non-renewable energy resources available in assumed regions across Ireland.

Region	Renewable Resource	Non-Renewable Resource
Northwest	Wind, hydro	Diesel, electricity grid
West	Wind, biomass, hydro	Diesel, electricity grid, natural gas grid

Southwest	Wind, solar, hydro	Diesel, electricity grid
South	Wind, solar, biomass	Diesel, electricity grid, natural gas grid
Southeast	Wind, solar, biomass	Diesel, electricity grid
East	Wind, solar	Diesel, electricity grid, natural gas grid
Midlands North	Biomass, biogas	Diesel, electricity grid
Midlands South	Solar, biomass	Diesel, electricity grid

Table 4.1. Adapted from “Regional integration of renewable energy systems in Ireland – The role of hybrid energy systems for small communities” by C. Goodbody, E. Walsh, K. McDonnell, & P. Owende, 2012, Electrical Power and Energy Systems.

The table 4.1 demonstrates that wind power is a prevailing renewable energy resource and is widely available in the Northwest, West, Southwest, South, Southeast, and East regions. Solar energy is somewhat less spread across the country and is mostly utilized in South and East regions where the climate is less dependent on the Atlantic weather front. The biomass resource is mostly available in each region since it can be stored and transported, and the biomass resource, however, is considered to be the key energy resource in the midlands where the fertile soil for the agricultural needs is located. Biogas has been identified as a key resource for the northern midlands. The hydropower is an essential energy resource for Northwest, West, and Southwest regions due to the high annual precipitation rate and specific topography in these areas (Goodbody et al., 2012).

Although micro-scale wind turbines are not yet capable of fully covering the annual average electricity load of a household, there is certainly a role for these technologies (Goodbody, 2012). As has been already mentioned, micro-renewable wind systems have demanding requirements in terms of location and since the installation of these projects in urban areas is associated with the range of considerable issues due to various obstructions in form of buildings and trees, which in their turn can considerably decrease the power of wind stream and consequently detrimentally affect the ultimate power output of the wind system, the best

settings for micro-scale wind exploitation technologies are considered to be well exposed suburban and rural areas with the average wind speed of not less than 6 m/s (IWEA, 2009), and according to the Central Statistics Office of Ireland (2012), the number of people dwelling in suitable settings is about 7 percent of total population of Ireland.

4.3.2 Selection of the Target Location

Since the focus of this study is on the application of micro-scale renewable energy systems in household settings, wind conditions of the target location need to be found out. Generally, Ireland has exceptionally good wind resource compared to the rest of Europe, especially in coastal locations, where wind speeds of 5 m/s at ground level and 7 m/s at 50 m height are not uncommon (SEAI, 2015). According to SEAI (2015) the Village of Youghal which is located in the south part of Ireland in the County of Munster can be taken as a target site for making projections on feasibility of the wind systems, because it represents the relevant conditions with average wind speed of 5.76 m/s at the level of 10 m above the ground in 2015 and can reach the speed up to 8 m/s at the latitude of 50 m above the ground (Fig. 4.2, 4.3).

Fig. 4.2 The location of the village Youghal.

Fig. 4.2. Adapted from: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Youghal>

Fig. 4.3 Wind speeds in Ireland at the latitude of 50 m.

Fig. 4.3. Adapted from: Wind Mapping Systems by Sustainable Energy Ireland, 2015, Dublin, <http://maps.seai.ie/wind/>

4.3.3 Micro Wind Turbines Available on the Irish Market

The microgeneration certification scheme is an independent scheme which certifies microgeneration systems and installers in Ireland and in the UK in accordance with the current legal standards and regulations. There is a range of registered micro wind turbines which fall under the certification scheme available on the Irish wind systems market. These turbines can be readily purchased from suppliers in Ireland and in the UK. The list of supplier in Ireland is quite long, the most popular models, however, are Ampair® 600 – 230V, Swift® 1.5 kW and Skystream® 3.7 (Fig. 4.3, 4.4, 4.5).

Fig. 4.4 Ampair® 600

Fig. 4.5 Swift® 1.5 kW.

Fig. 4.6 Skystream® 3.7.

Fig. 4.4. Adapted from:
<http://www.pwt.net.au/Manuals/Ampair%20600%20flyer.pdf>

Fig. 4.5. Adapted from:
<http://www.greenpacks.org/2009/02/12/swift-wind-turbine/>

Fig. 4.6. Adapted from:
<http://www.solarwindsenergy.com/products-skystream-3-7/>

The technology under investigation, the Energy Ball® V200, has a total capital cost of €7 100 and the annual energy output between 1 000 kWh and 2 250 kWh depending on the average annual wind speed, therefore the sample of the study will be based on two crucial for the average consumer parameters: the capital cost of the systems, which should not exceed €12 500 and the annual energy capacity which is in frames of 5 kWh. As has been already mentioned, today two systems which have similar characteristics and can therefore fall under the determined sample are available on the Irish market: Ampair® 600 – 230V and Skystream® 3.7 (Li et al., 2011).

In order to have a broader overview on the performance of the micro-scale wind turbines, one more wind system was also selected for the analysis. The usage name of the mentioned technology is Swift® 1.5 kW and although the system has the design which lies beyond classical three-rotor blades turbine shape, this technology needs to be also examined

upon the range of particular parameters since it falls under the determined conditions and therefore its performance can be compared with the performance of system under investigation which is Energy Ball® V200.

4.4 Limitations of the Study

The proposed methodology, however, is subjected to the range of certain limitations. First of all, the data regarding monthly and annual mean wind speeds can vary significantly from location to location and the results obtained in this study can considerably deviate from the results obtained using different numerical parameters and coefficients.

Second, it should be noted that the calculations will be entirely based on an average annualized electrical load profile and as has been already mentioned, the annual consumption rate totally depends on how many people live and how intensively electric appliance is used in the certain dwelling, hence, the numerical results for particular household can also have a considerable level of discrepancy from the results obtained in this study.

Third, all the financial outcomes will be obtained on the assumption of equal cash inflows throughout the entire lifespan of the system which is very unlikely to happen in reality.

Fourth, in this study the loan offered by financial institution is assumed to be covered within the entire lifespan of the system since different amounts of borrowed funds are subjected to different repayment periods and the actual information concerning minimum and maximum repayment periods offered by St. Patrick's Credit Union is unavailable (St. Patrick's Credit Union, 2016).

Finally, an annual inflation rate is not taken into consideration for this analysis since its prediction is quite a complex matter and can only be forecasted with quite high degree of uncertainty. However, since the lifespan of the systems reaches 20 years, this is an important factor that should be also addressed in future analysis.

5. Data Generation and Collection

This chapter of the thesis is devoted to the process of data collection and data generation which consists of several steps. The data on the average wind speed in the selected target location and the data on the average electricity household load will be generated by using the simulation software HOMER described in the previous part. The obtained numbers are required for further computations and analysis on cost effectiveness of the selected wind systems.

The second step is based on the collection of already existed and publicly available data on renewable energy regulations and policy, electricity prices and taxes, energy consumption rates in the residential sector and current situation on the renewable energy systems market in Ireland, which is necessary for obtaining the relevant and realistic results. Such a data can be retrieved from the platforms developed by Irish Wind Energy Association, Department of Communication, Energy and Natural Resources, Éireann, Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland, Central Statistics Office of Ireland and other governmental institutions which provide public access to the data storages.

5.1 Estimating Wind Resource at the Potential Micro-Wind Turbine Location

The process of establishing the number regarding wind resource in a potential target location is usually carried out by using special devices called anemometers which are mounted at the appropriate height with help of scaffolding poles and are able to measure turbulent fluctuations of horizontal and vertical wind (Sissons et al., 2011). The recorded data on wind speeds along three orthogonal axes are able to provide reliable and accurate results regarding wind profile in certain location (Campbell Scientific, 2016). This equipment is usually employed for determination of momentum flux and friction velocity of the wind in energy

studies conducted in field settings by scientific institutions which can afford to invest substantial amount of money in research (Sunderland, Mills & Conlon, 2011).

The relevant data on hourly wind speed can be also retrieved from the nearest meteorological station (Sissons et al., 2011) what is also not possible in this study.

5.1.1 Generation of Monthly Wind Speed

Since the hourly and monthly wind speed data for the selected target location cannot be obtained by any of the before mentioned approaches, artificial but statistically reasonable numbers for an entire year can be generated by applying software based wind prediction approach using HOMER.

In order to proceed with the study and to obtain the numerical data regarding effectiveness of the Energy Ball® V200, the monthly average wind speed within a year at the selected target location at which the system is to be exploited is required. Since the data on hourly and monthly mean wind speed are usually unavailable or too expensive to acquire, the annual average wind velocity is used in calculations. The absence of the data on monthly average wind speed, however, makes it impossible to obtain the data on realistic seasonal wind variations (Li et al., 2011).

A logarithmic wind speed profile is applied for computing the wind velocity at the micro turbine mast height if the mast height of the system differs from the altitude at which the measurements are performed. This is explained by the fact that wind velocity tends to rise in accordance with the height above the ground surface, since the obstacles in the form of buildings and trees decreases with height respectively (Li et al., 2011). A logarithmic wind speed profile exploits a surface roughness coefficient length in its computation. The surface roughness coefficient length is the parameter which characterizes the landscape conditions. In

this study the value which corresponds to a landscape conditions of an open field is equal to 0.1 (Seguro & Lambert, 2000).

The hourly wind speed data are derived by performing the range of complex statistical computations integrated in software. The calculations are based on the average monthly wind velocity data at the micro wind turbine mast height and four random variability parameters. These parameters are able to accurately reflect the wind settings for a specific target location and consequently ensure the generation of most reliable data on hourly wind velocity. In the study on economic viability of domestic micro-scale wind turbines Li et al. (2011) have described these four parameters and presented the values which represent the Irish conditions:

- Weibull k factor reflects the breadth of a distribution of wind velocities in the Weibull distribution which in its turn is a two-parameter function that is commonly applied to identify the wind speed frequency distribution (Seguro & Lambert, 2000). The value of 2.12 represents Irish conditions.
- Autocorrelation factor demonstrates how strongly the wind velocity in one particular hour depends on wind speeds in preceding hours. A value of 0.942 is used to represent Irish conditions.
- Diurnal pattern strength determines how strong wind velocities in the specific time of the day. The value of 0.152 corresponds to Irish conditions.
- Hour of peak wind speed is the hour of the day which is on average the windiest. 14:00 is considered to be the windiest day time across Ireland.

On the base of the aforementioned factors it is now possible to derive the data on monthly wind speed in the village of Youghal by applying the HOMER software. After inputting the range of the respective parameters we receive the value which is equal to 7.64 m/s. This number, however, represents the average wind speeds over 10 years on the height of

50 m above the ground (Fig. 4.4). For this study, therefore, the number on average wind speed provided by SEAI (2015) which is equal to 5.76 m/s will be taken since this value represents more realistic conditions.

Fig. 5.1 The data on monthly wind speed in Youghal generated by HOMER.

Fig. 5.1. Adapted from: NASA Surface meteorology and Solar Energy Database by US National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 2016.

In order to validate the data provided by SEAI (2015) I am going to elaborate on the historical wind data provided by Met Éireann (2016), the Irish national meteorological service, regarding average wind speed in the Cork Airport which is located on the similar geographic longitude at the distance of 56.7 km from the village of Youghal and is the nearest location where the wind speed measurements were taken by the official governmental meteorological institution. The table 5.1 demonstrates monthly average wind speed during the years 2014 and 2015:

Table 5.1 Monthly average wind speed in the Cork Airport for the years 2014 and 2015.

2014				2015			
Month	Speed (m/s)	Month	Speed (m/s)	Month	Speed (m/s)	Month	Speed (m/s)
January	5.14	July	3.6	January	5.65	July	4.63
February	5.14	August	4.11	February	4.63	August	4.11
March	6.17	September	4.63	March	5.14	September	4.11
April	6.17	October	4.63	April	4.63	October	8.3
May	5.66	November	3.6	May	5.14	November	6.17
June	4.63	December	5.66	June	4.63	December	7.2
Average Annual wind Speed is 4.92 m/s				Average Annual wind Speed is 5.36 m/s			

Table 5.1. Adapted from: Historical Climate Data for the Synoptic Stations, 2016, Dublin, <http://www.met.ie/climate-request/>

According to the data retrieved from the Met Éireann database (2016), the average annual wind speed over the years 2014 and 2015 in the Cork Airport is equal to 4.92 m/s and 5.36 m/s respectively. The average wind speed over these two years, consequently, is equal to 5.14 m/s.

As has been already mentioned, wind speed tends to be higher in the locations adjacent to coast line and since the village of Youghal is located right on the Celtic Sea cost, we can assume that this area is more exposed to strong wind streams than the Cork Airport which does not have the direct access to sea or ocean. Therefore, the value representing annual average wind speed in the village of Youghal which is equal to 5.76 m/s, provided by the SEAI (2015), can be considered as sufficiently grounded number and can be taken for delivering further projections on wind systems profitability. The respective adaptations, however, should be

considered in future analyses in order to represent more precise wind conditions in the selected area.

5.1.2 Generation of Household Electric Load

Hour-by-hour household electrical load can be also generated by using HOMER. An hourly-based electrical load profile for one day in a year is a minimum requirement. Then, the software is capable of synthetizing 8 760 hourly electrical load values for an entire year by utilizing this hourly electrical load profile and applying random variability parameters which are represented by day-to-day which is 4.46 and time-step parameter which is 10.8 (Fig 5.2) (Li et al., 2011).

Fig. 5.2 The data on the average hourly household electric load in Youghal generated by HOMER.

Fig. 5.2. Adapted from: NASA Surface meteorology and Solar Energy Database by US National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 2016.

After inserting the aforementioned variables I have obtained the numerical data regarding the average hourly household electrical load in Ireland which are presented in the following table:

Table 5.2 The average hourly household electrical load presented in numbers.

Time	Load	Time	Load	Time	Load	Time	Load
1:00	0.348 kW	7:00	0.537 kW	13:00	0.680 kW	19:00	1.020 kW
2:00	0.299 kW	8:00	0.600 kW	14:00	0.620 kW	20:00	1.000 kW
3:00	0.276 kW	9:00	0.601 kW	15:00	0.710 kW	21:00	0.970 kW
4:00	0.270 kW	10:00	0.629 kW	16:00	0.810 kW	22:00	0.820 kW
5:00	0.286 kW	11:00	0.660 kW	17:00	0.990 kW	23:00	0.630 kW
6:00	0.373 kW	12:00	0.700 kW	18:00	1.090 kW	24:00	0.348 kW

The following diagram graphically illustrates the electrical load during the day:

Fig. 5.3 The average hourly household electrical load in Ireland.

Having all the numbers retrieved by using the HOMER software it is now possible to compute the average daily and annual household energy consumption rate which is statistically grounded and close to the realistic figures presented by the Irish governmental institutions:

- the daily household electrify load is equal to 15.38 kWh;
- the annual average household energy consumption rate is 5 613.7 kWh, we can round the number and the ultimate figure which will be applied in further calculations on cost effectiveness of the selected systems is 5 614 kWh.

5.2 The Current Micro Wind Turbine Situation in Ireland

One of the first questions asked by the customers interested in investing in microgeneration project concerns the average price of a micro-scale wind system? Nowadays, the considerable number of micro-scale wind turbines is available on the Irish market. This range includes models which have certain important differences in terms of capital cost, electricity output, lifespan, and operation and maintenance costs which ultimately shape the purchase price of the certain turbine. For a specific target site the selection of the wind system and supplier are the vital factors which can eventually lead to either success or failure of the renewable energy project. The cost of grid connected turbine systems typically ranges from approximately €20 000 to €30 000 for 6 kW units and from €10 000 to €20 000 for a 3 kW unit. The price for micro-scale wind systems with the energy output of around 1 kW can vary from €3 000 to €7 000 (IWEA, 2014).

5.2.1 The Current Micro Wind Turbine Market in Ireland

Although micro renewable electricity generation is not yet very popular option in Ireland, it is far more demanded than any other type of system for electricity generation from renewable energy sources (Fig. 5.4) (Li et al, 2011).

Fig. 5.4 Breakdown of grid-connected micro renewable electricity generation devices installed from January 2007 to February 2010.

Fig. 5.4. Adapted from “Domestic application of micro wind turbines in Ireland: Investigation of their economic viability” by Z. Li, F. Boyle, & A. Reynolds, 2011, *Renewable Energy*, p. 65.

579 micro wind turbines with total installed capacity of 2 227 kW have been registered by Electric Ireland and connected to the Electricity Supply Board Networks in the period from January 2007 to February 2010. This accounted for 84% of the total installed capacity of grid-connected micro-renewable electricity generation systems within this period (McCarthy, 2010). The total capacity of installed micro wind turbines, however, is likely to be much higher, as the certain number of micro wind turbines is either used to connect with batteries or waiting to be connected to the national electricity grid (Li et al., 2013).

Large capacity (> 3 kW) micro-scale wind projects are the preferred options among the Irish householders to-date. Of the 2 227 kW (579 units) of micro wind turbines installed in Ireland between 2007 and 2010, approximately 80% have a capacity greater than 3 kW (Fig. 5.5) (Li et al., 2011).

Fig. 5.5 Breakdown of capacity of grid-connected micro renewable electricity generation devices installed from January 2007 to November 2011 in Ireland. The total installed capacity in this period was 2 227 kW.

Fig. 5.5. Adapted from ‘Domestic integration of micro-renewable electricity generation in Ireland - The current status and economic reality’ by Z. Li, A. Reynolds, & F. Boyle, 2011, *Renewable Energy*, p. 246.

5.3 Technical Specifications of the Sampled Micro-scale Wind Systems

In order to proceed with the future analysis it is crucial to identify the parameters and specifications of the system under investigation which is Energy Ball® V200 and the systems which correspond to the determined sample and will be later compared in analysis part. The data are obtained from the official websites of the manufacturers, brochures and manuals and are presented in the upcoming sections.

5.3.1 Micro-renewable Wind System Energy Ball® V200

As has been already mentioned, the Energy Ball® V200 is a micro-scale wind exploitation technology developed in the Netherlands by the company HomeEnergy. The device has a spherical shape formed by 5 curved rotor blades with the total diameter of 1.98m. According to the manufacturer, on the assumption of suitable weather conditions, the system is able to cover a substantial energy demand of the average household and, besides, HomeEnergy claims that the device is almost soundless and casts almost no shadow (HomeEnergy, 2009).

The Energy Ball® V200 is initially equipped with the energy inverter therefore is able to convert the DC electricity generated by the system to AC electricity which is suitable for delivery to the utility grid. The energy inverter connects to the home electrical breaker box therefore the power generated by the Energy Ball® V200 can be readily available for own home usage. The surplus energy not utilized by home owner, will be automatically exported to the national electricity grid (HomeEnergy, 2009).

The Energy Ball® V200 reaches its maximum capacity at wind velocity of 19 m/s and is generally capable of generating 1 750 kWh per annum on the assumption of the mean wind speed is approximately 6 m/s and the system is installed in well exposed open area without obstructions on the pole height of 10 m.

The key specifications of the Energy Ball® V200 are adduced in the table 5.3.

Table 5.3 Technical specifications of the Energy Ball® V200 system.

General	Minimum Wind Velocity	3 m/s
	Maximum Wind Velocity	40 m/s
	Rotor Speed Control	Not required
	Measured Output at 10 m/s	400 W
	Maximum Output at 19 m/s	2 250 W
	Annual Energy Production (at mean wind speed between 5.5 and 6 m/s)	Approximately 1 750 kWh
	Maximum RPM (rotations per minute) at 40 m/s	700 RPM
	Turbine Weight	90 kg
	Pole Height	8.5 m / 10.5 m
	Pole Weight	350 kg / 420 kg
	Pole Height with Ball	10 m / 12 m
	Number of Rotor Blades	5
Rotor Diameter	1.98 m	

	Lifespan	20 years
	Spinning Surface	3.8 m ²
	Acoustic Emissions at Wind Speed of 8 m/s	44 dB
	Brake System	Electric
	Capital Cost (Euro)	7 100
	Annual Maintenance Cost (Euro)	50
Generator	Electric Drive	3-phase
	Solenoid Generator Type	Permanent Neodymium
Inverter	Net Voltage	230 VAC (Volt Alternative Current) / 50 Hz

Table 5.3. Adapted from “Energy Ball® V200 Wind Energy Presentation” by HomeEnergy, 2009.

The sound emissions level of the Energy Ball® V200 was estimated by Lichtveld Buis & Partners BV (2009), commissioned by HomeEnergy. The results provided demonstrate that the sound pressure level of the system is extremely low (Lichtveld Buis & Partners BV, 2009).

Measurements were taken at different standardized wind speeds. Only when the wind reaches speed of 9 m/s the sound level produced by the system becomes higher than the background sound level generated by the wind stream itself (Table. 5.4).

Table 5.4 Energy Ball® V200 sound emissions at different wind speeds.

Standardized Wind Speeds [m/s]	Background sound pressure levels [dB(A)]	Sound pressure level of the Energy Ball® V200 at 50 m distance [dB(A)]
5	42.1	37
6	42.7	39
7	43.5	42
8	44.4	44
9	45.4	47

Table 5.4. Adapted from “Energy Ball® V200 Sound Level Report” by Lichtveld Buis & Partners BV, 2009.

5.3.2 Micro-renewable Wind System Ampair® 600

The Ampair® 600 is the micro-scale wind driven generator designed and manufactured by the company Ampair based in the UK. The system is capable of supplying up to 600 W of electrical power at either 12 or 24 volts for charging batteries or delivering electricity directly to the dwelling via grid-tie inverter. Ampair® 600 consists of the generator, the rectifier, the set of field wiring, the mounting, a current regulator and either batteries or grid-tie inverter depending on the customer's preferences (Ampair, 2007).

The system is specifically optimized for the target areas with low and medium wind speeds and according to the manufacturer may be applied in a wide variety of locations, including sailing yachts, holiday homes, remote detached houses, medical facilities, emergency shelters, scientific and environmental monitoring stations, remote industrial locations, telecommunication systems and is in generally developed with the aim to reduce dependence of in-grid connected homes, offices and commercial units on the national electricity supply network (Ampair, 2007).

The key technical data on the Ampair® 600 are outlined in the table 5.5.

Table 5.5 Technical data on the system Ampair® 600.

Nominal Power	600 W
Reference Annual Energy (at mean wind speed between 5.5 and 6 m/s)	Approximately 1 300 kWh
Rated Wind Speed for Nominal Power	12.6 m/s
Cut-in Wind Speed	3 m/s
Cut-out Wind Speed	none
Survival Wind Speed	Storm proof
Rotor Diameter	1.7 m
Hub Height	10 m
Number of Blades	3

Blade Material	Glass reinforced polyester
Rotor Speed	500 – 1 400 RPM
Generator Type	Permanent magnet, 3 phase with external rectifier
Nominal Voltage	12 V DC, or 24 V DC or 115 V AC / 60 Hz, or 230 V AC / 50 Hz
Speed Regulation	Blade pitch control above 13 m per second
Power Regulation	Blade pitch control above 13 m per second
Brake	Generator short circuit
Weight	16 kg
Color	White
Rotor Thrust (at the wind speed of 20 m/s)	800 Newtons
Capital Cost (Euro)	4800
Annual Maintenance Cost (Euro)	50
Product Lifespan	15 years

Table 5.5. Adapted from ‘Ampair® 600 Wind Turbine Operation, Installation & Maintenance’ by Ampair, 2007.

5.3.3 Micro-renewable Wind System Skystream® 3.7

The wind exploitation technology with the usage name of Skystream® 3.7 is developed and manufactured by the American company Southwest Windpower, Inc. in collaboration with the U.S. Department of Energy’s National Renewable Energy Laboratory and is particularly designed for owners of the utility-connected home and businesses looking for ways to reduce their monthly electricity bills by harnessing wind energy on a residential scale (Southwest Windpower, Inc., 2010).

The Skystream® 3.7 is a down-wind direct-drive permanent magnet wind generator. Since this micro-scale wind turbine represents an all-inclusive wind generator with in-built

inverter and control systems users are enabled to take advantage of gaining profits by exporting the generated electricity to the national power grid (Southwest Windpower, Inc., 2010).

According to the Southwest Windpower, Inc. (2010) the system is capable of starting energy generation at extremely low wind speed of 3.5 m/s and reaches its full output capacity at the wind velocity of 10.3 m/s. The Skystream® 3.7 can be mounted on the pole height starting from 10.6 meters and up to 33.5 meters, besides the manufacturer argue that the system demonstrates exceptionally quiet operation with the sound emission rate not exceeding 50 dB which is “quieter than background noise in a home or office” (Southwest Windpower, Inc., 2010).

The data on the technical specifications of the system Skystream® 3.7 are described in the table 5.6.

Table 5.6 Technical data on the system Skystream® 3.7.

Rated Power Capacity (Wind Speed of 11 m/s)	2 100 W
Max Power Capacity	2 600 W
Rated Annual Energy Output (at mean wind speed between 5.5 and 6 m/s)	Approximately 4 800 kWh
Rotor Diameter	3.72 m
Weight	77 kg
Swept Area	10.87 m ²
Type	Downwind rotor with stall regulation control
Direction of Rotation	Clockwise looking upwind
Number of Blades	3
Blade Material	Fiberglass reinforced composite
Rotor Speed	50 – 330 RPM
Grid Feeding	120 / 240 VAC Split 1 Ph, 60 Hz 120 / 208 VAC 3 Ph compatible

Battery Charger	Battery charger kit available for battery charging systems
Cut-in Wind Speed	3.5 m/s
Rated Wind Speed	13 m/s
Cut-out Wind Speed	63 m/s
Hub Height	10.6 m / 33.5 m
Color	White
Acoustic Emissions (Wind Speed of 8 m/s)	50 dB
Capital Cost (Euro)	12 500
Annual Maintenance Cost (Euro)	125
Product Lifespan	20

Table 5.6. Adapted from: <http://www.xzeres.com/wind-turbine-products/xzeres-skystream-3-7wind-turbine/>

5.3.4 Micro-renewable Wind System Swift® 1.5 kW

Another popular wind energy exploitation system in Ireland is called Swift® 1.5 kW and is manufactured by the company Renewable Devices Ltd. located in Scotland which was designed to meet the energy demand of small wind and on-site usage (Renewable Devices Ltd., 2010).

The sound suppression technology is implemented in the micro-wind turbine Swift® 1.5 kW by using the special diffuser ring which circles the blades and redirects wind flow in such a way that air flow passes through the blades over a much larger surface area and over a much smoother course. This ring is not only the key to the exceptional acoustic performance, making it aerodynamically silent, but also gives the turbine its trademark circular shape, the Renewable Devices Ltd. (2010) argues.

Technical specifications of the systems Swift® 1.5 kW are provided in the table 5.7.

Table 5.7 Technical data on the system Swift® 1.5 kW.

Turbine Type	Upwind Horizontal Axis with Acoustic Diffusor Ring
Rotor Radius	1.0 m/1.04 m diffusor
Swept Area	3.4 m ²
Hub Height	10 m
Gross Weight	37 kg (52 kg including rotor assembly)
Cut-in Speed	3.4 m/s
Cut-out Wind Speed	22 m/s
Rated Wind Speed	12 m/s
Annual Energy Production (at mean wind speed between 5.5 and 6 m/s)	Approximately 1 550 kWh
Rated Power Output	1.5 kW
RPM at Rated Wind Speed	450 RPM
Generator	Permanent magnet
Governing Type	Angle furling / Dynamic brake
Governing Wind Speed	14 m/s
Shut-down Mechanism	Dynamic Brake
Number of Blades	5
Grid-tie Version	Standard product (including inverter)
Electrical Network Versatility	50 Hz / 60 Hz 220 V / 230 V US, UK & Europe
Battery Charging Version	Available on demand
Phase Configuration	Single
Mounting System Available	4 mounting systems available
Acoustic Emissions at Wind Speed of 8 m/s	45 dB
Product Lifespan	20 years design life
Capital Cost (Euro)	7 000
Annual Maintenance Cost (Euro)	50

Table 5.7. Adapted from ‘Swift™ Wind Energy Systems Technical and Planning Pack by Swift™ Wind Energy Systems, 2010.

5.4 Irish Renewable Energy Legislation and Policy

Regardless of how the renewable energy system is reliable and promising, the promotion of the technology on the national market can be a highly complex matter if there is no governmental support for a specific program or the range of governmental regulations which tend to block any attempts to introduce the technology to the potential consumers exists. In this part I will investigate the current Irish renewable energy regulations.

5.4.1 Governmental Support for Renewable Energy Sources Utilization

From the mid 1990's the Irish government has proclaimed its intention to reduce carbon dioxide emissions by adopting a more environmentally conscious strategy and implementing international policies and regulations such as United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change and Kyoto Protocol. The last aims to limit Ireland's greenhouse emissions by 13% of emission levels recorded in 1990. In 2008 Ireland agreed to the EU Climate Energy Package that aims to reduce the greenhouse emissions by 20% below the emission level recorded in 1990 (Fig. 5.8) (SEAI, 2012).

Fig. 5.6 Ireland's Greenhouse Gas Emissions 1990 – 2014.

Fig. 5.6. Adapted from ‘Ireland’s Provisional Greenhouse Emissions in 2014’ by Environmental Protection Agency, 2014, Wexford.

In December 2010 the Irish minister of finance Brian Lenihan made a decision to increase the carbon tax from €15 per tonne to €20 per tonne of emissions (Daly, 2011).

The Kyoto Protocol has been expired in 2012 but Ireland remained committed to its target focused on reduction of CO₂ emissions and climate change mitigation and keeps following its initial target. According to the Energy Policy Framework 2007 – 2020 adopted by the Irish Government in 2007 renewable energy is to cover for 40% of gross national energy consumption by 2020 (Daly, 2011).

Even though there is a range of grants available for heating systems implemented in Irish households there are no grants for the installation of domestic wind turbines available in Ireland to-date (Daly, 2011).

5.4.2 Renewable Electricity Feed-in Tariff

Since early 2006, Renewable Electricity Feed-in Tariff (REFIT) became the primary tool for promoting renewable energy source technologies. Feed-in tariffs are guaranteed for up to 15 years, but may not extend beyond 2024. During its first year, 98% of the newly introduced support has been provided to the large wind energy projects (Daly, 2011), but in May 2010 the Prime Minister of Ireland Eamon Ryan announced the new Governmental program which aimed to support the price structure for renewable energy technologies utilized by private householders. The guaranteed support price under the Renewable Feed-in Tariff was from €0.15 per kWh to €0.09 per kWh depending on the integrated system (SEAI, 2015).

In general, €0.09 is paid to the most Irish householders by Electric Ireland for every kWh of electricity exported to the national grid from generated by micro-scale power system (Li et al., 2013). This price is a standardized payment and there are no restrictions of the amount of the electricity exported. Previously there was additional financial governmental incentive of €0.10 for every kWh for the first 3 000 kWh of feed-in electricity per year. This incentive was provided by the Electric Ireland and was applied for a maximum of five years in order to encourage private householders to use the micro-renewable energy generation systems (SEAI, 2009). This support, however, was cancelled in February 28th, 2012 (Li et al., 2013).

The tariff works according to a sliding scale, which gives an opportunity to ensure a guaranteed stable price for each unit of electricity exported to the national grid by paying the difference between the wholesale electricity price and the price under the REFIT. On practice, it means that as prices for electricity provided by Electricity Supply Board of Ireland raise, the amount paid under REFIT decreases, which is supposed to significantly alleviate the electricity bills burden for regular consumers (SEAI, 2015).

5.4.3 The Current Regulations for Installation of Micro Wind Turbines in Ireland

Installation of micro wind turbines in Ireland is normally a subject to planning permission. The installation of micro wind systems in domestic, industrial, agricultural and commercial settings, however, may be exempt from planning permission if it complies with certain terms and conditions (Li et al., 2011). These regulations for exemption from planning permission are explicitly stated in the Irish government report Planning and Development Regulations 2007 prepared by the Department of Environment, Heritage and Local Government (2007). These conditions are the following:

- The turbine shall not be erected on, or attached to, the house or any building or any other structure within its curtilage.
- The total height of the turbine shall not exceed 13 m.
- The rotor diameter shall not exceed 6 m.
- The minimum clearance between the lower tip of the rotor and ground level shall not be less than 3 m.
- The supporting tower shall be a distance of not less than the total structure height (including the blade of the turbine at the highest point of its arc) plus 1 m from any party boundary.
- Noise levels must not be higher than 43 dB(A) during normal operation, or in excess of 5 dB(A) above the background noise, whichever is greater, as measured from the nearest adjacent inhabited house.
- No more than one turbine must be installed within the curtilage of the dwelling.
- No structures shall be erected, placed or constructed forward of the front wall of a house.
- All the turbine components shall have a matt non-reflective surface and the blades shall be made of material that does not swerve telecommunication signals.

- No sign, advertisement or object not related to or required for the functioning or safety needs of the system shall be attached to, or exhibited on, the wind turbine (Department of Environment, Heritage and Local Government, 2007).

If the installation of a domestic-scale wind system does not match these requirements, it must undergo the planning process and there is still a high probability to get the permission, particularly if the turbine does not satisfy height requirement only.

In order to protect the grid, the maximum export capacity from a grid-connected micro-renewable electricity generation system shall not exceed 6 kW when the connection is single phase and 11 kW when the grid connection is three phase. The micro-renewable wind energy system with the ultimate total power output exceeding the aforementioned limits can still be connected to the grid once the maximum export capacity is constrained to the required values of 6 kW and 11 kW for one and three phase connections respectively. According to the Irish renewable energy regulations micro-renewable systems with the total energy capacity of up to 50 kW are eligible for connection to the national electricity grid (SEI, 2009).

All the sampled micro-scale wind systems are legitimate for the installation in Ireland since their technical and performance parameters comply with the current governmental regulations on micro-wind technologies.

5.5 The Household Electricity Situation in Ireland

According to Howley et al. (2008) the average annual electricity consumption load for a house in Ireland was 5 557 kWh in 2008. The level of electricity consumption has increased with an average annual growth rate of 4.1% from 1990 to 2008. This growth in electricity consumption is due to the reasons associated with the doubling of the average number of

household electrical appliances during that period. The average house in Ireland is also responsible for approximately 3.2 tonnes of greenhouse gas emissions per year (SEAI, 2009).

There are three main electricity suppliers in the county: the Electricity Supply Board, Airtricity and Bord Gáis. The Electricity Supply Board was established in 1927 and is a state institution which is controlled and owned by the Irish government. This body was the main energy supplier to households until the 19th of February 2005 when the Irish government made a decision to diversify the electricity market and open it for competition. Since that time the Airtricity has re-entered the Irish energy supply market and the new player Bord Gáis joined the fight for the local customer. Irish householders were able to decide which supplier to select and were able to freely switch from one company to another. The Commission for Energy Regulation, the state regulatory body for the electricity and natural gas sectors in Ireland, has restricted the Energy Supply Body (ESB) in their right to change its prices, to encourage the competition on the market and to let the other players gain their market share. The switch rate from the ESB to the other energy suppliers, however, was initially low and the market share of ESB by the end of 2008 was close to 80% which means that if the share exceeded this number the constraints imposed by the Commission for Energy regulation in regard to the price policy would have been abrogated. The situation changed in 2009 and the energy market experienced the high rate of switching among the consumers. As a result ESB lost a considerable market share of the domestic electricity supply market between 2009 and 2010. However, it still remained the largest energy supplier in Ireland, retaining almost 68% of the market in the middle of 2010 (Fig. 5.9) (Commission for Energy Regulation, 2010).

Fig. 5.7 Household electricity supplier market share (GWh) in Ireland in December 2009, March 2010 and June 2010.

Fig. 5.7. Adapted from “Factsheet: Competition in Electricity Supply” by Commission for Energy Regulation, 2010, Dublin.

According to the Central Statistics Office of Ireland (2012) the average household consists of a married couple with two children, living in a detached 3 bedroom house. This house is grid connected and uses gas and electricity just as much as an average Irish household consumes annually. The average annual electricity consumption for household was estimated is approximately 5 500 kWh (Howley, Ó Gallachóir & O'Leary, 2008), however the actual consumption rate entirely depends on the actual number of individuals living, the usage of appliance in the house and life preferences and habits of the dwellers in general.

The current imported electricity price supplied by the ESB based on the Irish Electric 24 hours Tariff is €0.25 per kWh. This price includes VAT at the rate of 13.5% and the Public Service Obligation Fee what ultimately makes the energy costs for the Irish householders among the highest in Europe (Electric Ireland, 2015). The electricity price in Ireland (including all taxes) was on average 6.6% higher than the average price of the 27 EU countries in 2009 and was ranked the seventh most expensive (Fig. 5.8) (Howley et al., 2010).

Fig. 5.8 Average electricity price for households per 100 kWh in second half of 2014.

Fig. 5.8. Adapted from: <http://www.thejournal.ie/electricity-ireland-2132930-May2015/>

6. Data Analysis

Although renewable energy sources have been dynamically developing for the past few years, there is still a noticeable lack of trust in wind energy and legitimacy of this kind of investment among Irish population. Such a situation might arise as a result of the wind turbines manufacturers' marketing policies, which sometimes provide inaccurate or even unrealistic figures regarding possible output of the proposed solutions and also try to conceal from their customers the environmental and technological factors that might have considerable influence on the technology efficiency in certain regions (Bukala et al., 2015).

A wide set of studies with the aim to derive the realistic output numbers and to determine the actual economic viability of one or another SWT were conducted, however, since most of the experiments are generally oriented to a particular geographic location, it is quite a complicated matter to obtain the ultimate answer regarding economic viability and cost effectiveness of the particular system.

According to Tummala et al. (2015), small scale wind turbines can be most beneficial if they are sized properly and used in their optimum conditions. Li et al. (2011) and Kellner and Ringwood (2009) in their studies on the economic viability of micro-scale wind systems for domestic application in Ireland confirm this idea by saying that such systems look promising when they are applied in areas with relatively high average wind velocity, e.g. higher than 6 m/s. Besides, according to Tummala et al. (2015), small scale wind turbines can become a valuable power source for remote areas which are located far away from grid powers. The perspective growth of this technology, however, heavily depends on the cost at which electricity is generated. Tummala et al. (2015) argue that two major factors which define cost effectiveness of wind turbine exploitation are the initial cost per W power and the unit cost per kWh produced by SWT. In case if these two parameters are within the affordable price range, small scale wind turbine can indeed become a useful source of energy generation.

6.1 Net Present Value and Payback Period Calculations

As has been mentioned in the Method part NPV parameter is applied in order to perform cost effectiveness analysis and to identify the economic viability of the optimal system in the particular settings (Eschenbach, 2011). Payback method in its turn delivers an answer on how many years are required for the certain project to break-even.

In order to avoid the flood of long and cumbersome calculations in the paper, they will be worked out with help of the financial application developed by Pearson Inc. and Microsoft Excel 2013 in which the aforementioned metrics are integrated.

The most relevant data on the selected wind turbines which are the Energy Ball® V200, the Ampair® 600 and the Swift® 1.5 kW are provided in the table 6.1:

Table 6.1 The annual energy output of the wind systems on the assumption that average wind speed is equaled to 5.76 m/s.

Wind Turbine	Capital Cost (Euro)	Annual Operation and Maintenance Cost (Euro)	Lifespan of the System	Reference Annual Power (Average Wind Speed is 5.76 m/s)	Hub Height
Ampair® 600	4 800	50	15	1 300 kWh	10 m
Swift® 1.5 kW	7 000	50	20	1 550 kWh	10 m
Energy Ball® V200	7 100	50	20	1 750 kWh	10 m
Skystream® 3.7	12 500	125	20	4 800 kWh	10.6 m

6.1.1 NPV and Payback Period of the Systems under Default Irish Settings

The Net Present Value and the payback period of the sampled micro-scale wind systems will be calculated by applying financial equations described in the Method part on the assumption of the current Irish conditions which are adduced below:

- The annual average speed in the selected target location which is the village of Youghal is equal to 5.76 m/s at 10 m height above the ground.
- A green loan rate offered by St. Patrick’s Credit Union in Ireland is equal to 5.5% (St. Patrick’s Credit Union, 2016).
- The annual household energy consumption of 5 614 kWh is used in this study. This number was obtained by applying the HOMER software. All the Net Present Value and payback period calculations for every selected system are based on this electricity load rate.
- An imported electricity tariff is €0.25 per kWh.
- An exported electricity price is €0.09 per kWh.

Taking into account the aforementioned variables, the NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems are presented by the following numbers:

Table 6.2 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems under default Irish conditions

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 966.74	20.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 2 469.22	18.3
Skystream® 3.7	21 500	1 075	346.66	11.6

Table 6.2. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity tariff is €0.09.

6.1.2 The Effect of Household Energy Load on NPV and Payback Period of the Systems

As has been mentioned before, the annual household electrical load entirely depends on the number of occupants, their live habits and on how intensive the usage of electric appliance in the house is. The energy generated by any of the selected micro-scale wind exploitation systems is most likely to be fully utilized as the average annual energy consumption rate used in this study which represents Irish conditions is 5 614 kWh which is quite high and any of the selected systems is not capable of covering the full energy demand.

Let us now presume that the average annual power consumption rate decreased by 75%, 50% and 25% and now the annual average electrical load rate is 1 403 kWh, 2 807 kWh and 4 210 kWh respectively.

The following tables demonstrate how NPV and payback period of the micro-wind systems vary depending on the changes in average annual household electricity load.

Table 6.3 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with average annual power consumption rate of 1 403 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 279.6	313.98	- 3 247.81	22.3
Energy Ball® V200	6 639.6	331.98	- 3 132.71	21.4
Skystream® 3.7	10 629.6	531.48	- 6 148.61	23.5

Table 6.3. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

Table 6.4 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with average annual power consumption rate of 2 807 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 966.74	20.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 2 469.22	18.3
Skystream® 3.7	15 122.4	756.12	- 3 464.07	16.5

Table 6.4. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

Table 6.5 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with average annual power consumption rate of 4 210 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 966.74	20.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 2 469.22	18.3
Skystream® 3.7	19 612	980.6	- 781.45	12.7

Table 6.5. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

6.1.3 The Effect of Feed-in Tariff Price on NPV and Payback Period of the Systems

The amount of energy generated by wind exploitation system might exceed the household electrical demand, especially if the power requirement rate of the certain dwelling is low. Previously, the surplus electricity generated was imported back to the grid for free in Ireland and the feed-in tariff was introduced to incentivize household owners to consider various micro-wind solutions (Li et al., 2011). The extra financial income generated other than from savings associated with reducing amount of imported electricity is supposed to help increase NPV and reduce payback period of the micro-wind systems. The current renewable energy feed-in tariff in Ireland which is €0.09 per kWh of exported energy (SEAI, 2015) is, however, very unlikely to increase cost effectiveness of micro-wind power generation systems as Li et al. (2011) argue.

Let us now assume that the Irish government made a decision to increase the price offered for the exported electricity by €0.03, €0.06 and €0.09 per kWh of returned energy. In the following set of calculations the price of €0.12, €0.15 and €0.18 per kWh of exported energy will be considered and in order to carry out the detailed analysis of changes in NPV and payback period of the selected micro-wind systems caused by increasing the renewable energy feed-in tariff, the three previously assumed average annual power consumption rates which are 1 403 kWh, 2 807 kWh and 4 210 kWh will be taken.

The default annual electricity load for the average household was defined on the level of 5 614 kWh and since any of the system is not capable of generating this amount of energy to fully cover the average energy demand, the changes in the exported electricity price are irrelevant for this scenario.

Table 6.6 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with exported electricity price of €0.12 and annual average household electricity load of 1 403 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 367.8	318.39	- 3 195.11	21.9
Energy Ball® V200	6 847.8	342.39	- 3 008.3	20.7
Skystream® 3.7	12 667.8	633.39	- 4 930.74	19.7

Table 6.6. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25.

Table 6.7 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with exported electricity price of €0.12 and annual average household electricity load of 2 807 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 966.74	20.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 2 469.22	18.3
Skystream® 3.7	16 318.2	815.91	- 2 749.56	15.3

Table 6.7 Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25.

Table 6.8 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with exported electricity price of €0.12 and annual average household electricity load of 4 210 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 966.74	20.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 2 469.22	18.3
Skystream® 3.7	19 966	998.3	- 569.93	12.5

Table 6.8. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25.

The following range of figures will be computed on the assumption that the feed-in tariff has been increased by €0.06 and now is equal to €0.15 per kWh of the exported electricity.

Table 6.9 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with exported electricity price of €0.15 and annual average household electricity load of 1 403 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 456	322.8	- 3 142.41	21.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 056	352.8	- 2 883.9	20.1
Skystream® 3.7	14 706	735.3	- 3 712.88	16.9

Table 6.9. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25.

Table 6.10 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with exported electricity price of €0.15 and annual average household electricity load of 2 807 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 966.4	20.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 2 469.22	18.3
Skystream® 3.7	17 514	875.7	- 2 035.05	14.3

Table 6.10. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25.

Table 6.11 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with exported electricity price of €0.15 and annual average household electricity load of 4 210 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 966.74	20.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 2 469.22	18.3
Skystream® 3.7	20 320	1 016	- 358.41	12.3

Table 6.11. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25.

The last assumption is that the exported electricity price has been increased by €0.09 and now the presumed incentive price offered by the Irish government to the householders for

every kWh of the returned electricity generated by micro-wind system to the national energy grid is €0.18.

Table 6.12 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with exported electricity price of €0.18 and annual average household electricity load of 1 403 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 544.2	327.21	- 3 089.71	21.4
Energy Ball® V200	7 264.2	363.21	- 2 759.5	19.5
Skystream® 3.7	16 744.2	837.21	- 2 495.02	14.9

Table 6.12. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25.

Table 6.13 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with exported electricity price of €0.18 and annual average household electricity load of 2 807 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 966.74	20.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 2 469.22	18.3
Skystream® 3.7	18 710	935.49	- 1320.53	13.4

Table 6.13. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25.

Table 6.14 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with exported electricity price of €0.18 and annual average household electricity load of 4 210 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2039.66	17.4
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 966.74	20.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 2 469.22	18.3
Skystream® 3.7	20 674	1 033.7	- 146.89	12.1

Table 6.14 Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25.

6.1.4 The Effect of Imported Electricity Tariff on NPV and Payback Period of the Systems

The imported electricity price is an important factor which can significantly influence the profit generated by the system in form of higher or lower amount of saved funds and consequently can considerably influence the eventual cost effectiveness of the certain wind system. As a benchmark prices the electricity price in Bulgaria which is €0.094 and is considered the lowest one among the European Union states and the current electricity price offered by the energy authority in the Netherlands which is €0.307 per kWh and is considered to be the highest energy price in EU-28 for household consumers (Eurostat, 2015) will be taken for the analysis.

Table 6.15 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with imported electricity price of €0.094 and annual average household electricity load of 5 614 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	1 083	72.2	- 4 075.28	66.5
Swift® 1.5 kW	1 914	95.7	- 5 856.34	73.1
Energy Ball® V200	2 290	114.5	- 5 731.68	62
Skystream® 3.7	6 524	326.2	- 8 601.78	38.3

Table 6.15. Loan rate is 5.5%, exported electricity price is €0.09.

Table 6.16 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with imported electricity price of €0.307 and annual average household electricity load of 5 614 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	5 236.5	349.1	- 1 295.88	13.7
Swift® 1.5 kW	8 517	425.85	- 1 910.92	16.4
Energy Ball® V200	9 745	487.25	- 1 277.17	14.6
Skystream® 3.7	26 972	1 348.6	3 616.28	9.3

Table 6.16. Loan rate is 5.5%, exported electricity price is €0.09.

6.1.5 The Effect of Wind Speed Variations on NPV and Payback Period of the Systems

The annual average wind speed is approximately 5.5 m/s in the midlands across Ireland, however, this number can increase by 7.5 m/s for some parts of the country, particularly along the coast line (O'Rourke et al., 2009). Furthermore, the results regarding the annual mean wind speed in the village of Youghal obtained by applying the HOMER software demonstrate that the annual wind speed in the selected target location can reach up to 7.64 m/s at the height of 50 m. In order to analyze the effect of the changes in wind speed on the profitability of the

selected wind turbines, let us now assume that the annual wind speed at the height of 10 m above the ground has increased by 7.64 m/s

Since the precise numbers of the electricity output generated at the wind speed of 7.64 m/s are unavailable, we can obtain the data by applying the proportion equation, which is:

$$x = \frac{S_1 E}{S_2} \quad \text{Eq. 6.1}$$

Where:

- x – the unknown annual energy output;
- S_1 – the assumed wind speed (7.64 m/s);
- S_2 – the actual wind speed (5.76 m/s);
- E – the actual annual energy output (kWh).

The assumed numbers regarding annual energy generation rate of the selected wind systems are provided in the following table:

Table 6.17 annual energy output of the wind systems on the assumption of average wind speed is equaled to 7.64 m/s

Wind Turbine	Capital Cost (Euro)	Annual Operation and Maintenance Cost (Euro)	Lifespan of the System	Reference Annual Power (Average Wind Speed is 7.64 m/s)	Hub Height
Ampair® 600	4 800	50	15	1 724 kWh	10 m
Swift® 1.5 kW	7 000	50	20	2 055 kWh	10 m
Energy Ball® V200	7 100	50	20	2 321 kWh	10 m
Skystream® 3.7	12 500	125	20	6 367 kWh	10.6 m

The following set of calculations will be carried out as for the default annual household electrical load so for the three other electrical load scenarios. The results will demonstrate how the NPV and the payback period of the systems may vary under the aforementioned assumptions.

Table 6.18 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with average wind speed of 7.64 m/s and annual average household electricity load of 1 403 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 944.6	329.64	- 1 491.21	14.5
Swift® 1.5 kW	7 188.6	359.43	- 2 704.67	19.4
Energy Ball® V200	7 667.4	383.37	- 2 518.58	18.5
Skystream® 3.7	13 450.2	672.51	- 4 463.24	18.6

Table 6.18. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

Table 6.19 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with average wind speed of 7.64 m/s and annual average household electricity load of 2 807 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	5 715	381	- 975.68	12.6
Swift® 1.5 kW	9 275	463.75	- 1 458.01	15.1
Energy Ball® V200	10 605	530.25	- 763.3	13.4
Skystream® 3.7	17 943	897.15	- 1 788.71	13.9

Table 6.19. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

Table 6.20 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with average wind speed of 7.64 m/s and annual average household electricity load of 4 210 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	5 715	381	- 975.68	12.6
Swift® 1.5 kW	9 275	463.75	- 1 458.01	15.1
Energy Ball® V200	10 605	530.25	- 763.3	13.4
Skystream® 3.7	22 432.6	1 121.63	903.9	11.1

Table 6.20. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09

Table 6.21 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with average wind speed of 7.64 m/s and annual average household electricity load of 5 614 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	5 715	381	- 975.68	12.6
Swift® 1.5 kW	9 275	463.75	- 1 458.01	15.1
Energy Ball® V200	10 605	530.25	- 763.3	13.4
Skystream® 3.7	26 925.4	1 346.27	3 588.44	9.3

Table 6.21. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

6.1.6 The Effect of Loan Rate on NPV and Payback Period of the Systems

Costs associated with the purchase of a wind exploitation system usually represent quite a substantial investment for the majority of householders in Ireland. Therefore, the interest rate on the loan provided by financial institution can also be a highly essential factor for making an ultimate decision in favor or against installation of the wind system. The green loan which falls under the category of home improvement loans is nowadays available in many banks and credit unions in Ireland. Bank of Ireland currently offers a loan rate of 7.5% (Bank of Ireland, 2016) and Ulster Bank offers a loan rate of 8.5% (Ulster Bank, 2015). For this study the green loan rate offered by St. Patrick's Credit Union in Ireland, which is 5.5% (St. Patrick's Credit Union, 2016) was taken for determining the cost effectiveness of the wind systems, because this loan rate is among the lowest ones available in Ireland to-date.

To identify the dynamics of NPV associated with the changes in loan rates, let us now assume that the loan rate offered by St. Patrick Credit Union was decreased by 50% and the new annual percentage rate represents 2.75% and the second scenario is the opposite one: the percentage rate was raised by 50% and is now equal to 8.25% per annum.

As has been already mentioned the dynamics of payback period is not considered in this part since the data on the repayment period entirely depends on the amount of loan and is not available for the selected systems.

Table 6.22 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with annual percentage rate of 2.75% and annual average household electricity load of 5 614 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 1 456.9	-
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 1 860.8	-
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 1 199.43	-
Skystream® 3.7	21 500	1 075	3 869.29	-

Table 6.22. Imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

Table 6.23 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with annual percentage rate of 8.25% and annual average household electricity load of 5 614 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 2 481.65	-
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 3 747.12	-
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 3 365.21	-
Skystream® 3.7	21 500	1 075	- 2 138.99	-

Table 6.23. Imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

6.1.7 The Effect of Capital Grant Availability on NPV and Payback Period of the Systems

Since the high capital cost is one of the most significant obstacles that can make householders refrain from installing micro-wind exploitation systems, a capital grant can be a key incentive for all the individuals interested in utilization of renewable energy in their

dwellings (Li et al., 2011). There is no grant currently available in Ireland for micro-wind turbines, unlike heat pumps, solar thermal systems and biomass boilers (SEAI, 2015).

Let us now assume that Sustainable Energy Authority Ireland or any other Irish government body made a decision to provide financial support for individuals interested in purchasing of micro-wind systems. To perform an analysis of this option, let us presume that the grant which worth 5%, 10% and 20% is now available for wind energy technologies. In the following table the cost of the wind turbines on the assumption of the three capital grant options is provided:

Table 6.24 Capital Costs of the sampled wind systems calculated according to the three assumed capital grants.

Wind Turbine	Capital Cost without Capital Grant (Euro)	Capital Cost with 5% Capital Grant (Euro)	Capital Cost with 10% Capital Grant (Euro)	Capital Cost with 20% Capital Grant (Euro)
Ampair® 600	4 800	4 560	4 320	3 840
Swift® 1.5 kW	7 000	6 650	6 300	5 600
Energy Ball® V200	7 100	6 745	6 390	5 680
Skystream® 3.7	12 500	11 875	11 250	10 000

Now on the basis of the newly derived costs of the wind systems, we can obtain the new numbers regarding NPV of the sampled systems and their payback periods.

Table 6.25 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with capital grant of 5% and annual average household electricity load of 5 614 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 1 799,66	16.6
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 616.74	19.7
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 2 114.22	17.4
Skystream® 3.7	21 500	1 075	971.66	11

Table 6.25. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

Table 6.26 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with capital grant of 10% and annual average household electricity load of 5 614 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 1 599,66	15.7
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 2 266.74	18.6
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 1 759.22	16.5
Skystream® 3.7	21 500	1 075	1 596.66	10.5

Table 6.26. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

Table 6.27 NPV and payback period of the sampled micro-wind systems with capital grant of 20% and annual average household electricity load of 5 614 kWh

Wind Turbine	Lifespan Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Annually Generated Cash Flow (Euro)	Net Present Value (Euro)	Payback Period (years)
Ampair® 600	4 125	275	- 1 079.66	13.9
Swift® 1.5 kW	6 750	337.5	- 1 566.74	16.5
Energy Ball® V200	7 750	387.5	- 1 049.22	14.6
Skystream® 3.7	21 500	1 075	2 846.66	9.3

Table 6.27. Loan rate is 5.5%, imported electricity price is €0.25, exported electricity price is €0.09.

7. Discussion and Interpretation of Findings

The cost effectiveness analysis of the selected micro-scale wind systems was performed in the previous part with all the relevant assumptions. The interpretation of findings will be provided in the following chapter where all the peculiarities and characteristics of the obtained results will be described. In order to demonstrate correlations between NPV and payback periods of the systems and the considered factors all the dynamics is expressed graphically by using diagrams created with help of MS Excel 2013.

7.1 Default Irish Conditions

The payback period and the Net Present Value for the four micro-scale wind turbines have been worked out and having a look at the table with the numbers obtained by applying the parameters corresponding to the default Irish conditions, one can see that the only system which has a positive NPV and a reasonable payback period, therefore can be considered economically viable under the given settings, is Skystream® 3.7. The system Energy Ball® V200 has a negative NPV, however, the system's payback period is in frames of its lifespan, which is 20 years, unlike two other selected technologies.

Fig. 7.1 NPV and Payback Period of the Systems under Default Irish Conditions

7.2 Discussion on the Effect of Household Energy Consumption Rate

As has been already mentioned, the amount of electricity generated by any of the selected wind systems is most likely to be fully utilized since the average electrical load in Ireland is quite high and according to the results obtained by using HOMER software is currently equal to 5 614 kWh. On the other hand, if the electrical load is low, the surplus energy can be exported to the national electricity grid. Therefore, the changes in annual level of electricity consumption have a significant effect on the cost effectiveness of wind exploitation systems and their payback period. In order to demonstrate this dynamics, three scenarios with three different annual energy consumption rates were considered. All the findings will be benchmarked against the numbers obtained under the default Irish conditions and will be demonstrated graphically.

The following diagrams demonstrate dynamics of the NPV and payback period of the systems on the assumption that the annual electrical load is equal to 1 403 kWh.

Under the aforementioned assumption one can see that there is no system which can be considered economically viable. The Net Present Value is highly negative for every system and any of the sampled turbines is not capable of paying off the investment within its lifespan. Since the assumed electrical load is quite low, there is certain amount of electricity left which can be fed-in to the national grid, the money, however, earned by importing the surplus energy are of small significance and cannot meaningfully influence cost effectiveness of the sampled systems. Therefore, micro-scale electricity generation wind turbine is not a rational solution for the household with low annual electrical load rate.

The second scenario was made on the assumption that annual average power consumption rate was equal to 2 807 kWh.

One the diagram provided one can see that under the aforementioned annual electrical load the NPV and the payback period for the systems Ampair® 600, Swift® 1.5 kW and Energy Ball® V200 are now equal to the numbers received under default Irish conditions because any of the system is not capable of reaching the energy output of 2 807 kWh. The only changes happened in NPV and payback period of Skystream® 3.7. These changes are quite substantial since the NPV of the system increased by €2 684.54 and the payback period decreased by 7 years. The electrical load, however, is still cannot be considered sufficient for implementing micro-scale wind solution.

The last scenario was based on the assumption of annual consumption rate which was equal to 4 210 kWh.

As well as for the previously assumed annual electrical load, the changes in NPV and payback period occurred only for the system Skystream® 3.7. The NPV and the payback period are close to the NPV and the payback period obtained by applying default Irish parameters, however, these numbers are still lower than results obtained under default Irish settings.

The effect of annual electrical power consumption rate is an important factor when considering one or another wind energy exploitation technology. Although low electrical load rate allows householders export the surplus energy to the national electricity grid, with the current exported electricity price of €0.09 per each kWh these cash inflows are much lower in comparison to cash inflows which can be obtained by savings made through implementation of

own wind energy exploitation system, therefore, the smaller the electrical load in household the less economically viable the system.

7.3 Discussion on the Effect of Feed-in Tariff Price

In case if electricity generated exceeds the household electrical load required it will be exported to the national energy grid. The current price for each kWh of the exported electricity in Ireland is €0.09. The analysis was based on the assumption that the price was increased by €0.12, €0.15 and €0.18 per every kWh exported to the national electricity grid. The dynamics was investigated on the assumption of previously mentioned scenarios based on the three different annual average energy consumption rates which are 1 403 kWh, 2 807 kWh and 4 210 kWh.

In this part the numbers received on the base of the default parameters are irrelevant since any of the systems is not capable of generating 5 614 kWh, therefore, there is no energy left to export to the national electricity grid.

The following diagrams demonstrate the changes in NPV and payback periods of the systems according to the three aforementioned exported electricity prices on the assumption that the annual electrical load is equal to 1 403 kWh.

According to the diagrams, the NPV and payback period dynamics are positively changing if the exported electricity price grows. No changes occurred only for the system Ampair® 600, because its energy output is too small. With the exported electricity price of €0.18 The NPV of the Energy Ball® V200 increased by €248.8 and its payback period decreased by 2.4 years. The NPV and the payback period of the system Skystream® 3.7 were again subjected to the most substantial changes because under the presumed household annual electrical load this system is able to generate a huge amount of surplus energy which can be exported to the national grid, so, the higher the feed-in tariff the higher the system’s NPV and the shorter the payback period.

The next scenario with the annual electrical load of 2 807 kWh was considered.

With the annual average electrical load of 2 807 kWh the NPV and the payback period of the systems Ampair® 600, Swift® 1.5 kW and Energy Ball® V200 are no longer exposed to any changes, because these systems do not generate extra energy which can be exported to the grid. The NPV and the payback period of Skystream® 3.7 were again subjected to positive changes, the NPV, however, still remains highly negative.

The last scenario under investigation is based on the annual energy consumption rate of 4 210 kWh. And the diagrams demonstrate the following results:

Under the aforementioned scenario the changes in NPV and in payback period occurred only for the wind system Skystream® 3.7 and with the exported electricity price of €0.18 and with the assumed annual electrical load the system's NPV almost reached zero.

In this part three presumed exported electricity prices were worked out on the base of three electrical load scenarios. The conclusion is the higher the feed-in electricity tariff, the more likely the certain system can become economically viable. According to Li et al. (2011) the currently offered exported electricity price is too low to make micro-scale wind systems attractive investment, it has also been proved empirically in the analysis part and one can see that even with the assumed tariff which is €0.18 per every kWh of exported energy which is two times higher than the feed-in price offered by the Irish energy authority nowadays, the NPV of every system remains negative meaning that householders are very unlikely to meaningfully benefit from cash inflows associated with exporting energy to the national grid.

7.4 Discussion on the Effect of Imported Electricity Tariff

Micro-wind exploitation system can indeed become a rational investment in case if the imported electricity price is quite high because installation of own electricity generation system can allow householders to reduce consumption of energy provided by governmental power suppliers therefore to save significant amount of funds. The current imported electricity tariff in Ireland is €0.25 per kWh and the analysis of this parameter was made on the base of two scenarios: the new imported electricity tariff is equal to the electricity price in Bulgaria which is €0.094 per kWh and the current electricity price in the Netherlands which is €0.307 per each kWh of imported electricity according to Eurostat (2015). The results will be benchmarked against the default parameters in order to demonstrate the dynamics of the systems' NPV and payback periods.

Fig. 7.14 NPV of the Systems Depending on the Changes in Imported Electricity Tariff

Fig. 7.15 Payback Period of the Systems Depending on the Changes in Imported Electricity Tariff

On the diagrams provided above one can see that the imported electricity tariff is indeed among the most crucial factors which have a profound influence on NPV and payback period of the certain system. The higher the national imported electricity tariff, the more economically viable micro-scale wind exploitation system and the higher its NPV. With the imported electricity price of €0.307 the NPV of Energy Ball® V200 increased by impressive 51.72% and its payback period shortened by 3.7 years.

These changes are caused by the strong positive correlation between the raising imported electricity price and the increasing amounts of funds saved due to substituting the power provided by national suppliers to the electricity generated by own wind exploitation energy system. The increasing imported electricity tariff demonstrates the strong negative correlation with payback period of the systems, since the higher the imported electricity price, the shorter the payback period of the particular electricity generation turbine.

7.5 Discussion on the Effect of Wind Speed Variations

Weather conditions at the particular target location where wind systems are installed play an essential role in determining their cost effectiveness. The average annual wind speed is probably the most important parameter which is usually the first one to pay attention when considering installation of wind exploitation system because wind power eventually defines the ultimate amount of the electricity generated and consequently determines if one or another wind system is economically viable or is not. The stable and strong annual wind speed in certain location can make even a wind turbine with small capacity economically attractive investment and conversely, the lack of wind power can become a decisive factor against installation of wind system even with the very promising amount of energy output.

The average annual wind speed in the village of Youghal which is the target area for this study is approximately 5.76 m/s. This wind speed was taken as a default parameter and all

the NPV and the payback period calculations were worked out on the base of this metric. In order to demonstrate how changes in average annual wind speed can influence the profitability of micro-scale wind system the speed of 7.64 m/s was applied in the analysis.

The analysis was made for four scenarios based on four various average annual electrical loads which are 1 403 kWh, 2 807 kWh, 4 210 kWh and 5 614 kWh which is the default one. All the diagrams will be again benchmarked against the numbers obtained by applying the default wind speed which is 5.76 m/s.

On the given diagrams one can see that although NPV is negative and payback period of the systems is quite long both indicators significantly positively changed with the higher average annual wind speed.

Another scenario was based on the assumption of annual electrical load which is equal to 2 807 kWh. The following diagrams will demonstrate how NPV and payback periods vary depending on the changes in annual wind speed in comparison to numbers received under default wind conditions.

Fig. 7.18 NPV of the Systems Depending on the Changes in Annual Average Wind Speed with the Annual Electrical Load of 2 807 kWh

Fig. 7.19 Payback Period of the Systems Depending on the Changes in Annual Average Wind Speed with the Systems Depending on the Changes in Annual Average Wind Speed with the Annual Electrical Load of 2 807 kWh

Due to higher average wind speed the turbines are now capable of generating more substantial amount of electricity than under default wind speed which is 5.76 m/s. Since the energy output increased significantly it was positively reflected on the NPV and payback periods of the selected systems. As for Energy Ball® V200 it is now capable of covering almost the entire electrical load of 2 807 kWh and although its NPV is still negative it was increased by €1 705.92 and the payback period decreased by almost 5 years what now makes the system indeed an attractive investment under the assumed conditions.

The following diagrams demonstrate the dynamics of the systems' NPV and payback periods under the assumption of annual electrical load of 4 210 kWh and the average annual wind speed of 7.64 m/s.

Under the aforementioned assumption the only system which demonstrated changes in its NPV and payback period is Skystream® 3.7. Under the assumed electrical load the system's NPV becomes positive therefore the system becomes cost effective under the given conditions. Since any of the other selected turbines are no longer capable of generating the amount of energy to cover the assumed electrical load of 4 210 kWh their NPVs and payback periods were not subjected to any changes.

The last scenario is based on the power consumption rate derived by applying the HOMER software. The electrical load rate is equal to 5 614 kWh and is close to the number provided by IWEA (2015) which is 5 557 kWh.

Fig. 7.22 NPV of the Systems Depending on the Changes in Annual Average Wind Speed with the Annual Electrical Load of 5 614 kWh

Fig. 7.23 Payback Period of the Systems Depending on the Changes in Annual Average Wind Speed with the Annual Electrical Load of 5 614 kWh

The last set of diagrams demonstrates that if the average annual wind speed increases by 7.64 m/s, Skystream® 3.7 becomes a genuinely very attractive investments since it demonstrates the impressive NPV of €3 588.44 and the payback period of 9.3 years meaning that the system is supposed to function more than 10 years longer after it ultimately pays off.

7.6 Discussion on the Effect of Loan Rate

The default loan rate for making calculations on cost effectiveness of the sampled wind systems is equal to 5.5% and is offered by Saint Patrick's Credit Union (2016). In order to demonstrate how the changes in loan rate correlate with the changes in NPV and payback period of the systems two scenarios were assumed, where first implied the 50% decrease of the default loan rate to 2.75% and the second scenario was based on the assumption that the loan rate was raised by 50% to 8.25%. These assumptions will be benchmarked against the results calculated by applying default numbers on the following diagrams.

Out of the results obtained one can see that NPV of the systems significantly increased with the lower annual loan rate and conversely NPV tends to fall if the loan rate is growing.

Since the information regarding the actual repayment periods is unavailable in this study, it is difficult to investigate the correlation between changes in annual loan rates and payback periods. However, since the lower loan rate implies lower cash outflows and the higher loan rate increases the amount of investment for the householders, we can assume that the lower the loan rate offered by the financial institution the lower the cash outflows for the customers, what in turn shortens the payback period of wind systems.

The dynamics occurred in NPV of the systems due to the changes in annual loan rates demonstrates that this parameter is an essential factor when considering micro-scale wind solution, because with the high annual loan rate wind systems are very unlikely to become economically viable even if they are installed in high average wind speed locations.

7.7 Discussion on the Effect of Capital Grant Availability

According to SEAI (2015) there is no grant currently available in Ireland for micro-scale wind exploitation systems. In order to identify how the amount of capital grant may affect the NPV and payback period of the wind systems three scenarios were elaborated where the Irish government is ready to alleviate the financial burden of the customers interested in installation of wind energy technologies by providing the capital grants of 5%, 10% and 20%. To demonstrate the dynamics the new numbers will be graphically compared to the defaults results where the capital grant for micro-scale wind exploitation technologies is not available.

Fig. 7.25 NPV of the Systems Depending on the Amount of Capital Grant

According to the data provided one can see how strongly the availability of the governmental financial support affects NPV and payback periods of the selected wind systems. Literally every percent of capital grant added increases NPV of every system and shortens its payback periods. The correlation between the amount of capital grant provided and the profitability metrics is very strong and even the 5% capital grant has increased the NPV of the Energy Ball® V200 by 14.3% and decreased its payback period by almost one year, therefore, the higher the amount of capital grant the more economically viable the wind exploitation

system is. Therefore, capital grant is an important incentive which can genuinely make micro-scale wind systems a lucrative investment and if a proper financial support can be made available by Irish government bodies, micro-wind turbines can indeed become an attractive alternative energy technology in Ireland.

8. Conclusion

In this paper the technique for determining the cost effectiveness of four selected micro-scale wind systems which are commercially available and can be potentially installed in Ireland has been presented. Additional micro-scale wind exploitation systems can be added to the existing database if a wider range of micro-renewable energy systems is required for examination. A simulation and optimization software HOMER, Discounted Cash Flow and Payback Period methods were used to derive relevant numbers and to identify variations in economic viability due to changes in climate settings and financial incentives associated with installation of micro wind systems in particular target location.

There are seven appropriate assumptions made in this study. These assumptions have covered most of the scenarios which can potentially have a substantial impact on the future of Irish micro-scale wind exploitation systems market. This analysis is supposed to provide a relatively accurate and empirically grounded results obtained by applying relevant data available on the specific target location under the relevant technical and economic settings (Dalton, Lockington & Baldock, 2009). The purpose of the paper was to perform a broad cost effectiveness analysis of the four sampled systems and on the base of the results obtained to compare the data on performance of Energy Ball® V200 with the data on performance of the three competing wind systems and to give the ultimate answer on the research question which is ‘Is Energy Ball® V200 more cost effective than classic horizontal axis three rotor blades micro-scale wind turbines in the setting of Irish household?’

Out of the results obtained, one can see that under all the scenarios the system Energy Ball® V200 demonstrated a negative NPV, when the system was subjected to certain conditions, however, its NPV was close to zero making the system almost economically viable under certain climate and financial circumstances. Furthermore, the system's payback period was usually in frames of its lifespan unlike the two competing systems which are Ampair® 600 and Swift® 1.5 kW.

The NPV and the payback period of the system Energy Ball® V200 were subjected to significant positive variations under the scenario of the higher imported electricity price. The NPV of the system increased by 51.72% under the aforementioned assumption and its payback period decreased by 3.7 years and, although its NPV remained negative, if the imported electricity price kept increasing, this system could become cost effective with the reasonable payback period.

Investigation of influence of wind speed on performance of the sampled wind turbines demonstrated that micro-wind turbines are very unlikely to be economically viable if they are installed in regions with the annual average wind speed lower than 5 m/s and the higher the annual average wind speed the more economically viable the wind system is. In the case of Energy Ball® V200 with the higher average annual wind speed which was assumed to grow by 1.88 m/s the NPV of the system has increased by impressive 69.08% and its payback period shortened by 4.9 years.

According to Li et al. (2011) there is a large room for possible improvements to be done to increase the interest among the Irish population towards the micro-turbines market and to promote widespread installation from the government direction by providing financial support, changing electricity tariffs, implementing special green loan with a low interest rate. The investigation of the effect of changes in loan rates and availability of capital grant has

empirically proven that these two parameters are extremely important for the development of micro-scale wind systems market in Ireland and providing lower loan rates and considerable capital grants are among the key incentive approaches to encourage maximum number of householders to consider micro-scale wind energy solutions.

From this study, results show that Energy Ball® V200 can only become cost effective if it is subjected to certain conditions. The system, however, outperforms its closest competitor which is Swift® 1.5 kW in every scenario which gives the system a good chance to be potentially selected by the customers who are considering purchase of wind system with the capital cost in frames of €7 500. The highest dynamics can be observed in NPV and payback period of Skystream® 3.7 and the system has proven to be the most cost effective technology among the selected turbines, the price of the system is, however, €5 400 more than the price of the system under investigation and this factor can be a decisive one, since amount of money to be overpaid is quite considerable for the average Irish householder.

Even though the micro wind generation has yet to become very popular in Ireland due to high capital cost, uncertain cost effectiveness and long payback period for micro-scale wind turbines, the Irish government keeps making big efforts to promote micro-scale wind exploitation systems market by offering various financial incentive programs. One possible strategy is to increase the REFIT. This incentive can help micro-scale wind systems become indeed economically viable under certain conditions as a result this step can encourage householders to cover their energy needs. Another possible strategy might be implementation of the scheme that offers a financial incentive to householders who already try to meet the majority of their electricity demand by using renewable energy systems. The demand for micro wind electricity generation systems will certainly be increased if a substantial financial assistance can be provided from the Irish government (Dalton, Lockington & Baldock, 2009).

Although micro-wind generation turbines are by far more popular in Ireland than any other energy production system they are still unlikely to bring huge benefits for the owners unless put in specific circumstances described in the Analysis part. From the technical standpoint, one viable and possible solution to resolve the issue concerning covering the energy demand can be the coupling a micro-wind turbine and solar photovoltaic system (PVS). Such a combination can ultimately improve the power supply reliability and provide continuous energy stream despite variations in climate condition and weather (Li et al., 2013). Obtaining the answer on the optimal hybrid system might be, however, quite a complicated matter, further analysis on this potential option is required.

Ultimately, every householder should always make a personal decision depending on each individual case if a micro wind turbine is worth to be installed from the financial perspective, taking into account the local weather conditions, the availability of micro wind turbines and the financial incentives for micro wind generation systems. In addition to this, the world micro-scale wind turbine market is very dynamic and is being continuously influenced by changes and improvements in micro wind turbine technologies, the economies of scale in production and government regulations in Ireland.

9. References

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